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A Critical Discourse Analysis of Racism in Selected English Sports Reports on a Ballon d’Or Award 2024

A Thesis

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by

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﴿ وَمِنْ آيَاتِهِ خُلُقُ السَّمَاوَاتِ وَالْأَرْضِ وَخِطَابُ أَلْسِنِكُمْ وَأَلْوَانِكُمْ إِنَّ فِي ذَلِكَ لَآيَاتٍ لِّلْعَالَمِينَ ﴾

صدق الله العلي العظيم

(سورة الروم، آية ٢٢)

In the name of Allah, the Most Gracious, the Most Merciful

“And among His Signs Is the creation of the heavens And the earth, and the variations In your languages And your colours: verily In that are Signs For those who know.”

Allah, the Most High, the Most Great, has spoken the truth

Surah Ar-Rūm (22)

(Ali, 2004)

Supervisor's Certification

I certify that this thesis, which is entitled “A Critical Discourse Analysis of Racism in Selected English Sports Reports on a Ballon d’Or Award 2024,” written by Issa Sattar Dhiab Manther, has been prepared under my supervision at Mustansiriyah University in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Arts in English Language and Linguistics.

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Committee's Certification

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Dedication

To two blessed fruits of the Mohammedan tree:

To the awaited hope of justice and the divine proof

Imam Muhammed al-Mahdi (May Allah hasten his reappearance),

to the fountain of knowledge and the torchbearer

of wisdom Imam Ja'far al-Sadiq (peace be upon him).

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All praise is due to Allah, whose praise cannot be fully articulated by those who speak, whose bounties cannot be enumerated by those who count, and whose due right cannot be fulfilled by those who strive. He is beyond the reach of lofty aspirations and cannot be comprehended by the depths of intellect.

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To my martyred father, a star that lights up my sky; to my mother, whose prayers are the rain that nourishes my path; and to my friend, Issa Haider, a companion on this journey and a partner in ambition.

Abstract

Sports journalism in the realm of media landscape functions not only as a means for reporting outcomes but also as an influential discursive platform that creates social meaning, enhances dominant ideologies, and influences public perception. This study intends to investigate how racism and racial dynamics are framed in sports news reports, specifically, in the case of the Real Madrid football player Vinicius Junior (Vini Jr) and his exclusion from the 2024 Ballon d'Or. The problem addressed in the current study revolves around the way institutional injustice and racial bias are embedded in sports news reports and whether they resist or reinforce these biases. Accordingly, the study intends to identify the linguistic and discursive strategies used in the selected British and American sports reports to represent Vini's exclusion from the 2024 Ballon d'Or. Moreover, it investigates the roles of the lexical choices used in the selected reports and how these reports frame racism. Finally, this study explores the ideological implications of the racial dynamics associated with the award through the Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) approach. The analysis of the data selected is based on four questions, namely: (1) What are the discursive and linguistic strategies employed through the transitivity system to portray Vini's exclusion from the Ballon d'Or 2024 Award? (2) What are the roles of the lexical aspects in representing racial injustice? (3) How do the British and American journals frame racism? and (4) What are the ideological implications associated with the 2024 Ballon d'Or award? To achieve the aims and answer the proposed questions, 16 extracts are analyzed from two British sports reports, including the BBC and the Guardian, and two American ones, including ESPN and the New York Times. The study has been conducted through a qualitative research approach adopting an eclectic model involving Fairclough's three-dimensional framework (1989, 2001), based on Halliday and Matthiessen's Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) (2014), Fairhurst and Sarr's Framing Theory (FT) (1996), and Delgado and Stefancic's Critical Race Theory (CRT) (2001). The analysis findings have concluded that the British and American journals construct their reports based on the material and relational processes since they capture the major elements of how actions and relationships are represented in language. Moreover, ideologically, the British reports rely on the explicit declarations of racial injustice, while American journals focus on the ambiguity of reasons behind racism, avoiding direct claims to racial bias. Finally, the present study provides several recommendations and suggestions for further studies.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviated Form	Full Form
AAA	American Anthropological Association
AABA	American Association of Biological Anthropologists
AAPA	American Association of Physical Anthropologists
BBC	British Broadcasting Corporation
CDA	Critical Discourse Analysis
CL	Critical Linguistics
CLS	Critical Legal Studies
CRT	Critical Race Theory
DA	Discourse Analysis
DHA	Discourse-Historical Approach
ESPN	Entertainment and Sports Programming Network
FA	Football Association
FF	France Football
FIFA	Fédération Internationale de Football Association
FT	Framing Theory
SCM	Socio-Cognitive Model
SFL	Systemic Functional Linguistics
UEFA	Union of European Football Associations

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Chapter One

1.0 Introduction

This chapter presents full details concerning the background of the study to introduce the key terms and related concepts concerning football media and language. Moreover, the problem statement is introduced in the chapter. The questions and the aims upon which the study is built are specified. The study's procedures, limitations, and value are also presented in the chapter.

1.1 Background of the Study

The domain of sport, specifically football, is not just a physical domain but is intricately interrelated with language. Halone and Mean (2010), sport is primarily biased, showing that it is reproduced, enacted, and systematized by means of language and other communicative practices. Language serves as a crucial basis for athletic culture and as a means through which beliefs, norms, values, and traditional customs of a sporting field are communicated and sustained. These emphasize the socially formed nature of sport, through which language plays an important role in highlighting its strategies, rules, and the emotional experiences associated with it. Graf, Callies, and Fleischhacker (2023) state that football has witnessed a consistently rising popularity and huge coverage in different kinds of traditional associations and mass media.

Sport discourse intersects everyday language since people utilize idioms and metaphors of sports in ordinary speech. Brenner, Burns, and Ewald (2014) declare that televised football has affected household language (e.g., “hit a home run”, “drop the ball”, “Monday morning quarterback”). Linguists observe that sport discourse includes particular vocabulary that serves cultural functions, in which Fairclough (1995) asserts that “discourse is a socially constituted-

sports commentary both influences and reflects social relations” (p.18). Through language choices, fans and commentators build (sporting worlds) in which power, society, and identity relations are enacted (Fairclough, 2010). In such a case, the interaction of sport and language is sustained. Van Dijk (2008) affirms that, “sports not only create a unique jargon but also become a lens through which social meanings are communicated” (p.23).

Sport journalism serves as an influential discursive institution that shapes athletic events by means of a specific ideological lens, selectively presenting narratives that conform to dominant cultural values and commercial imperatives and even racial bias (Thompson, 1995). Sport is a phenomenon of both global importance and distinctive local appeal. Nicholson (2007) claims that the relationship between sports and media is fundamental to the cultural and political economy of sports. The value of sport to media institutions has increased massively, relating to the massive audiences and advertising associated with it. Simultaneously, the media have revealed an important capacity to affect the organizations, performance, and diffusion of sport by television, coverage, broadcasting rights, sponsorship, advertising, and recent influential media platforms (e.g., the internet and mobile phones). Indeed, media have played a crucial role in the transformation of sport from a hobby into a hyper-commercialized global institution (Maguire, 2004). It also contributes to the rise of sport as a dominant economic, social, and cultural force, both internationally and locally. Over two decades, academic concentration on the relationship between the media and sport, sometimes termed as “media sport,” has grown considerably (Bernstein & Blain, 2003). Rowe (2011) states that sports journalism occupies an important position in the news media, and it is economically significant in drawing readers to news publications.

The historical roots of racism in football can stem from long-standing cultural beliefs about natural biological differences between racial groups. Jonsson (2017) states that football stadiums

during the 1970s to 1980s remained aggressive spaces as overt racism was common. Richardson (2009) points out that football became a cultural mirror during the 1980s, as some fans described Black players with prejudice and discontent. This period witnessed extensive racist chanting and abuse within stadiums. Linguistically, such issues have been studied through the CDA, since it constitutes an important framework for examining football-related narratives, particularly in determining issues of racism, bias, and discrimination. Fairclough (2013) indicates that CDA uncovers how media narratives challenge racial hierarchies. Narratives are fundamental in legitimizing power relations and racial bias cases through framing events in ways that suit dominant ideologies. The focus of CDA on ideology enables academics to deconstruct these narratives and show their socio-political implications (Wodak & Meyer, 2016).

In sum, football has been broadly studied as a global cultural phenomenon, but its interconnections with discourse, ideology, and racism in journalism still need to be explored. Though many studies tackled various aspects of football discourse (Behnam & Jahanban, 2015; Rahimi & Sahragard, 2017; Olagunju, 2019; Indrawti, 2021; Ghaffori, 2023; Ong'onda, 2023; Makki, 2023; Mauro, 2024; Casado-Linares, 2025); still, the relation between racism, bias, and media discourse requires further investigation as far as the football award and the whole controversy surrounding it is concerned. The present study explores how non-European football players' selection in awards is influenced to great instance by different racial reasons as when happened in the Ballon d'Or 2024 with the Brazilian football player Vini who played a pivotal role in helping Real Madrid win both La Liga and Champions League in the 2023/2024 season scoring 24 goals and providing eleven assists to be snubbed later for the Ballon d'Or award 2024.

1.2 The Problem Statement

Football was created to promote values of equality and fairness via strengthening bonds of relationships between people and countries with its member associations. Racial biases and discriminatory discourses persist through media presentation of athletes. Currently, sports news reports have become an important field of research, especially when dealing with football events, news, competitions, and awards. Specifically speaking, football competitions, including the Ballon d'Or, are widely renowned for athletic events that are considered an effective source for constructing rich media news. The problem of the current study indicates that, despite all attempts to keep media journalism and football away from racism, controversial issues are still associated with racial bias. Sports news reports represent and frame racial bias, explicitly or implicitly, relying on different linguistic and discursive strategies (process types, lexical choices, framing techniques) that make it difficult to state how the journals are biased. The exclusion of Real Madrid player Vini from the Ballon d'Or, and the representation of the racial bias controversy by British and American journals, serve as a case study that implies ideological perspectives and reflects the significant influence of sport and media on public perception. Accordingly, the problem statement of the current study highlights the gap in stating how British and American journals represent and frame the controversial issue of racial bias concerning prestigious awards such as the Ballon d'Or, reflecting a biased nature through the critical analysis of language use and framing of ideological implementations.

1.3 Research questions

1. What are the discursive and linguistic strategies employed through the transitivity system to portray Vini's exclusion from the Ballon d'Or 2024 award?
2. What are the roles of the lexical aspects in representing racial injustice?

3. How do the British and American journals frame racism?
4. What ideological implications are associated with the 2024 Ballon d'Or award?

1.4 The Aims of the Study

The current study aims to:

1. Identify the linguistic and discursive strategies used in the British and American news sports reports selected to represent the racial bias, as far as Vini's exclusion from the Ballon d'Or 2024 is concerned.
2. Investigate the roles of lexical choices used in the selected reports.
3. Explore how British and American reports frame racism in the Ballon d'Or 2024 against Vini Jr.
4. Uncover the ideological implications of the racial dynamic associated with awards through the CDA approach.

1.5 The Procedures of the Study

To fulfill the aims of the study, the following procedures are followed:

1. Providing a literature review of the study's key concepts, including language, media, racism, sports journalism, CDA, SFL, FT, and CRT.
2. Collecting data from four British and American journals representing Vini Jr. and the Ballon d'Or 2024.
3. Adopting an eclectic model for the analysis of the data collected.
4. Conducting a content analysis based on the eclectic model.
5. Comparing and discussing the findings of the study.
6. Drawing conclusions based on the analysis, denoting recommendations and suggestions for further studies.

1.6 The Limits of the Study

This study is limited to the analysis of four journals, published by two British news outlets, BBC and The Guardian, and two American news outlets, The New York Times and ESPN, with a total of 16 extracts. Two reports were selected from each journal, and two extracts were analyzed for each report. Particularly, the study focuses on the media discourse surrounding Vini Jr. and the Ballon d'Or 2024. The data is analyzed through an eclectic model including Fairclough's three-dimensional framework (1989, 2001), based on Halliday and Matthiessen's SFL (2014), Fairhurst and Sarr's FT (1996), and Delgado and Stefancic's CRT (2001).

1.7 The Value of the Study

The present study will be useful in constructing knowledge and understanding of CDA, SFL, FT, and CRT, and more specifically, concepts related to language and football. Theoretically, it attempts to provide a major contribution to linguistics by analyzing how discourse sustains and constructs racial stereotypes within sports media. Also, academically, it provides a general reference for other researchers on the role of discourse in constituting ideologies, as well as useful insights and methodologies for the analysis of sports media and societal impacts. Moreover, socially, the study increases people's awareness of how language and media portrayals influence community perception.

Chapter Two

Literature Review

2.0 Introduction

This chapter provides a comprehensive literature review of language and sports, media representation in sports journalism, football discourse, and racism. The aforementioned key terms and concepts, including their definitions, history, and features, are presented in the chapter as well. The CDA approach with its basic concepts, such as ideology, power, dominance, hegemony, and critique, is given in detail. Further, the chapter involves an overview of an SFL, CRT, and FT. Additionally, this chapter provides references to the previous studies.

2.1 Language and Sport

Language and sport create a significant domain where communication strategies significantly reflect and shape cultural patterns in athletic competitions. The relationship between language and sport in linguistics intersects as a symbolic system with social hierarchies, elaborated codes, physical performances, and enhancing societal norms (Bernstein, 1971). In the field of CDA, the study of language within sports is pivotal for comprehending how sports narratives and reports shape identities, affect perceptions of performances, and manage power structures among different communities. Spurr (2001, p.82) states that the language of sport is mainly defined as “the linguistic representation of sporting activity, that is bodily effort in the situations of identifiable games with rules and procedures and of competitions”. The representation of sport in media, particularly television, radio, press, and internet, occupies a great position in the field of research (Taborek, 2014, p.237). The language of sport belongs to the history of journalism, which

is traced back to the 18th century. Modern journalism started about a hundred years ago with the industrialization related to newspapers in the late 19th century. Over time, sports coverage has extended primarily and is no longer confined to the back pages (Spurr, 2001). Language serves a useful purpose in sports for better communication. Players in the field use language to direct players, organize movements, and predict the opponent's actions. Training is used for encouragement and instruction. In these contexts, the purpose of the language extends beyond itself to achieve certain physical outcomes (Doran, 2022).

Several scholars have provided definitions that help to illustrate the complexity of language and sport. Language, on the one hand, Chomsky (1957) defines language as “a set of (finite or infinite) sentences, each finite in length and constructed out of a finite set of elements” (p.13). In other words, he considers all natural languages, either in written or spoken form, to include a finite number of sounds and a finite number of letters in their alphabet. On the other hand, the domain of sport is emphasized by its nature, positioned as a piece of evidence for human attempts and competitions (Chomsky as cited in Xia, 2024, p.1). Derbyshire (1967) declares that “language is undoubtedly a type of means of communication among humans, is composed primarily of vocal sounds. It is systematic, articulatory, symbolic, and arbitrary”. He emphasized the point that language is the property of human beings, which has been utilized from the initial beginning of human civilization as an independent tool or means of communication among human beings. There are no human events that eliminate language. “Language can be written or spoken; it can adopt non-verbal forms like Morse code, sign language, or other systems of signals” (Kurcz, 1976). “Language is an essential part of our lives. It allows personal communication through mental processes and creates an expression of our emotions, sensations, and feelings” (Kurcz, 1983). Laker (2002) affirms that “Sport provides a common ground, a safe arena for interactions in a wide variety of social settings because sport is a constant in the cultural milieu. Moreover, he declares

sport preverbs culture, not only in terms of media content and coverage, but also in terms of language and metaphor” (p.8). According to Kowalikowa (2009), sport is “a human activity aimed at one’s self-fulfillment, it satisfies both psychological and social needs of an individual, which together constitute a spectrum of one’s motivations and aspirations” (p.64). “Language is a dynamic and rule-governed process of communication, it includes written, spoken, or signed modalities, which enable cultural transmission, social interactions, and identity formation” (Crystal, 2010, p.401).

Taborek (2014, p.238) states that the language of sport can be recognized as “a specialized language or terminology”, with distinctive characteristics throughout diverse linguistic levels: the first level, a text-linguistic level, the language of sport includes many text types or genres. The most notable is football commentary, which varies depending on the field, radio, television, newspaper reports, modern digital platforms, and SMS notifications. Further text types contain news articles including player or coach quotes, statistical tables (top scorers, team ranking, match schedules), and profiles of players including accurate statistics and interviews. The second level is a pragmatic level, which includes distinct communicative contexts. For instance, relations between referees or between coaches and players are explored through pragmalinguistic analysis. Additionally, fan chants in football function as an expression of regional identity. Luhrs (2008) emphasizes how these chants play a key role in constructing regional and local identities, enhancing distinctions between teams and their competitors. The third level is a cognitive level in which the language of sport serves as a tool for conveying knowledge. It uncovers unique features through distinct linguistic levels, encompassing vocabulary, grammar, pronunciation, discourse, communication, and cognition (Taborek, 2014, p.238).

2.2 Media Representation in Sport Journalism

Media representation dealing with sport is fundamental in influencing cultural narratives, public perception, and ideological backgrounds surrounding athletes. Peter (2018) states that sports journalism is a well-structured and generally expanded part of the media, providing interpretation, results, and commentary to the population. In fact, sports journalism sustains a dominant presence across broadcast, digital, and print platforms. The relationship between media and sports is underlined by their mutual dependence, in which media platforms depend on sports for content that draws viewership, while sports organizations utilize media exposure to improve commercial culture and viability (Rowe, 2004).

Sports journalism, historically, has developed into a particularized domain with an important presence through distinct media platforms, and can trace its roots back to the 15th century (Stephens, 2007). Early sources of the concept of “sport” appeared in Italian writings from the 1400s, involving descriptions of an unspecified competition. It was not until the 18th century that the foundations of contemporary sports journalism began to emerge (Maguire, 1999). The origins of sports reports can be traced back to the 18th century, connected to the rise of general news publications (Betts, 1953).

In Britain, sports coverage basically focuses on local activities and betting, resulting in a commercial between sport and media (Walker, 2006). Precise publications like the sports and pastimes of the people of England appeared in the early 1800s, with the Sunday Times starting comprehensive sports coverage in 1822 (Boyle & Haynes, 2009). In America, sports reports were raised in the 1820s and 1830s (Betts, 1953). By the 1930s, sports reports became a new section in the media, in which news of football and test cricket was recognized as distinct from politics and other news (Boyle & Haynes, 2009).

The rise of television from the 1930s to the 1950s changed sports viewing, creating new benefits for fans but posing challenges for print journalists, who were waiting for the audiences who had watched the games (Miler, 2007). The influence of television extended to color broadcasts enhanced the popularity of sports such as cricket in India (Stewart & Smith, 2000). Al-Manaseer (2013) states that “mass media stand to all means of spreading cultural knowledge to the audience and recently have become the most powerful vehicles in the molding of beliefs, attitudes, and values” (p.1). In Britain, television in the 1990s helped to extend elite sports coverage (Boyle, 2017). However, the appearance of the internet in the 1990s presented new challenges for sports journalism. Nowadays, sports journalists play a key role beyond traditional duties, involving commentary, editing, and blogging, with social media and multimedia confusing their responsibilities (McEnnis, 2016).

Media representation in sports journalism is notable by a set of interconnected characteristics that influence its content, perception, and societal impact (Boyle, 2017, pp.15-22), and these are:

1. Narrative framing refers to the purposeful structuring of sports stories to determine particular themes, like (competition, heroism, and redemption) Boyle (2017), illustrates this framing “transforms athletic events into mythic struggles, where athletes act like heroes, villains, or undergoes to increase emotional resonance” (p.16).
2. Commercial imperatives rule media representation as sports journalism increasingly functions for corporate interests via sponsorship interaction, branded content, and the promotion of pay preview platforms. Boyle explains that “the symbiotic relationship between media outlets and sports journalism confirms that coverage usually prioritizes profitability over journalistic rationality” (p.18).

3. Ideological enhancement is revealed in the perpetuation of dominant cultural norms, like gender binaries, nationalism, and meritocratic ideals. For example, Boyle noticed that media representation normally “enhances athletes who conform to hegemonic masculinity while marginalizing those who challenge racialized or gendered patterns” (p.19).
4. Audience fragmentation explains the shift from mass-audience broadcasting to richer, digital communities, determined by particular platforms. Boyle (2017) states, “it breaks up communal viewing experiences, replacing common societal moments with content that is personalized and selected by algorithms” (p.22). Therefore, changing how sports narratives are interpreted and consumed.

The most exciting studies on sports journalism culture have been done by media sports researchers. However, some critics assert that sports journalism has not been studied enough, and the domain of sports media has been rising for a long time (Schultz, 2005; Boyle, 2006). This study intends to investigate the relationship between how racism is depicted in sports journalism and shaped by media globalization, altering it into a global form of entertainment and a powerful tool for cultural exchange.

2.3 Media Globalization in Football and Racism

The globalization of media has transformed football into a global event, enhancing cultural, economic, and political influence and intensifying systemic issues such as racism. Football is one of the most common sports worldwide, played in different settings from the favelas of Brazil and the slums of Africa to the iconic stadiums of Europe. Beyond the boundaries of a game, it functions as a source of inspiration, a cultural ritual, and a tool for breaking cultural and social barriers. Some players accomplish superstar positions, becoming iconic in the sport. Regardless of its unifying nature, football continues to experience events of racism, making it one of the sports most affected

by such issues (Sassoon, 2010). It is mainly accepted as the most trending sport in the world, and its trend continues to rise quickly. The processes of globalization have influenced the sale of television sports rights, the marketization of global sporting competitions, and new methods of media sports consumption via specialized, networked, and mobile media formats (Dashti, 2022).

Historically, the origin of football can be traced back to ancient civilizations, with similar games played in China (Cuju), Greece (Episkyros), and Rome (Hapastum) (Guttmann, 1994). Modern football started to take place in the 19th century in England, where distinct forms were played in schools and clubs (Williams, 1988). In 1863, the formation of the Football Association (FA) established the rules, separating football from rugby and highlighting kicking the ball, which led to the creation of the FA Cup in 1871 (FIFA, 1955). The formation of the Federation Internationale de Football Association (FIFA) in 1904 expanded the sport globally, leading to the inaugural FIFA World Cup in 1930, which was held in Uruguay, to become one of the most popular sports (Faraz, 2024).

Nowadays, football, as a worldwide famous sport, has a unique ability to unite different populations and enhance a shared identity, exceeding cultural and geographical boundaries (Gul, 2023). However, this uniting potential is dominated by the persistent issue of racism, which manifests in numerous forms, influencing players, fans, and the broader football society (Sport Integrity Australia, 2024). Accelerate (2025) states that Racism within sports clubs includes discrimination, prejudice, and unequal treatment based on ethnicity or race, taking the form of offensive gestures, racial slurs, or discriminatory behavior of players, coaches, management, or fans. Such issues can harshly influence an athlete's emotional and mental well-being, leading to feelings of exclusion and isolation. Moreover, racism contributes to depression and anxiety, which inhibit emphasis, motivation, and connection, influencing an athlete's performance on the field. Pap Ndiaye, in his book *La Condition Noire*, as cited in (Sassoon, 2010), explains how black

footballers in some European stadiums are subjected to aggressive behavior, like having bananas thrown at them, and compares them to apes as marked by the “human zoo”.

Media in its distinct forms play a diverse role in forming perceptions of race within football, acting as a mirror determining cultural biases and as a maker influencing public opinion. Media outlets, such as television and newspapers, have reported on racist incidents, bringing consciousness to these issues, but also at times sensationalizing them. The way media frames players and events can notably shape public perception of players based on their race (Compete, 2024). Essential events such as FIFA World Cup and other international competitions function as powerful unifying forces, bringing nations together in a shared passion for the game.

Although the term “globalization” was not coined till the second half of the 20th century, in the English language, the noun “globe” dates from the 15th century, derived from the Latin word *Globus* (Robertson, 2001). The adjective “global” emerged in the late seventeenth century, which means (world scale), and the verb “globalize” was revealed in the 1940s (Reiser & Davies, 1944). The term “globalization” as a process appeared initially in the English language in 1959 and entered the dictionary two years later (Schreiter, 1997, p.5). The globalization of media can be illustrated by Fiveable (2025) as:

Media globalization indicates the increasing interdependence and interconnectedness of media systems worldwide, determined by advancements in communication, technology, and cultural exchange. This notion influences language use, distribution, and access to different forms of media, leading to a blend of global and local societal expressions that can influence language development and change.

This interconnectedness, enabled by advancements in digital broadcasting and technologies, has enhanced both the positive and negative aspects of the game on a global scale (Faraz, 2024). Accelerate (2025) indicates that the widespread nature of global media means that instances of racism, whether on the pitch, online, or in the stands, are now immediately visible to

a worldwide audience, creating a crucial interplay between the sport, its globalized media representation, and the insistent challenge of racial prejudices.

According to Thompson (1995), media globalization can be characterized by certain features:

1. Large international media companies control most of the media trade.
2. These companies utilize new communication and information technologies.
3. They work in an environment with fewer government rules and restrictions.
4. The spread of the media worldwide, globalization has made various media products more alike and standardized.
5. Media globalization enhances consumerism and is closely linked to capitalism.

In sum, the globalization of media has evolved football into a global system that unites various audiences while intensifying persistent issues such as racism. This study intends to investigate the way media globalization influences public perceptions and understandings of sports reports, and how these reports reveal linguistic and discursive aspects to shape racism.

2.3.1 Framing Theory

The concept of framing was first introduced by Gregory Bateson (1972), who stated that framing is a psychological concept that refers to “a special and temporary bounding of a set of interactive messages” (p.197). That serves as a form of metacommunication (Hallahan, 2008), to illustrate the practice of thinking about news items and story content. Bateson (1972) states the concept of framing through two analogies, namely, a picture frame and Venn diagrams, which are utilized in mathematical set theory. Frame as a diagram involves elements of a mathematical set, focusing on two methods: to include elements within its borders and to exclude elements outside the borders. The frame as a picture organizes the recognition of people and the way they understand

things, by using individuals to know what is within it and to ignore what is outside it. Correspondingly to Gitlin's (1980) understanding of framing, claims that a frame is built on selection, emphasis, and exclusion. A specific frame makes people focus on messages (which are included within it) and ignore messages (which are excluded from it).

Goffman (1974) declared that frame analysis emphasizes that people illustrate what is going on around their world based on their central framework. According to him (1974), there are two divisions within the central framework:

- 1- Natural framework: Describe events as natural occurrences, without focusing on any social reasons or effects behind them.
- 2- Social frameworks: This view states events as formed by social actions and affected by people's goals, intentions, and manipulations. A social framework is based on natural ones, and this framework explains how we share, interpret, and understand information. Goffman claims that people utilize these frameworks daily, whether consciously or unconsciously.

Therefore, framing indicates drawing attention to specific attributes of the objects of news coverage. By structuring themes or ideas, ways of connecting historical stories, and creating a narrative over time and through political cases. Scheufele and Tewksbury (2007) explain the frames used via media as macro-constructs to reduce the complexity of the issues and to change them to be useful for audiences. Frames in the minds of individuals become micro-constructs that permit audiences to attain the received information to draw their picture and impressions about the world. Arowolo (2017) declares that "media frames are attributes of the news themselves, but individual frames are cognitive and information schemas" (p.431). Media frames are based on the use of media resources (spoken or written, moving or still images, visual or sound elements) to structure the specified story through which it is promoted.

According to Fairhurst and Sarr (1996), language is useful in remembering acts and information to transform how we view situations. To use language, individuals should have thoughts that would be reflected in their interpretative frameworks. Fairhurst and Sarr (1996) suggest specific techniques for framing:

- 1- **Metaphor:** To describe an idea or to systematize a new meaning by comparing it with something else.
- 2- **Stories:** To frame a topic with an anecdote clearly and unforgettably (legends and myths).
- 3- **Tradition:** To organize and describe an organization at proper time increments to reproduce and adapt organizational values.
- 4- **Jargons, slogans, and catchphrases:** To frame a topic remarkably and familiarly.
- 5- **Artifacts:** To clarify commercial values using physical traces.
- 6- **Contrast:** To describe a topic by referring to what it lacks or does not involve.
- 7- **Spin:** To state a concept by describing it with a negative or positive connotation.

FT (Neuman, Just, & Crigler, 1992) distinguishes between specific and generic frames. Generic frames are flexible and can be used across different cultures, places, and times, while specific frames are restricted to a certain event or topics; they cannot be used outside these contexts. Generic frames are valuable for comparing findings via various studies, making it easier to enhance general theoretical recognitions. However, applying specific frames may make such comparisons more difficult, they offer a greater understanding of how media presents specific issues and how this influences people. As stated by Semetko and Valkenburg (2000), generic frames such as (consequences, human impact, conflict, and economics) permit cross-study comparisons and theoretical generalizations.

2.4 Race: Key Terms and Concepts

Racism remains a deeply embedded and intricate challenge in the modern era, changing in different ways that sustain inequality and injustice. According to Bonilla Silva (2017), understanding its diverse nature involves a comprehensive examination of its foundational concepts, historical advancement, reproduction in cultural domains like sports media, and the challenges faced by global organizations in combating it. Recognizing the concepts and key terms of racism is fundamental to exploring its manifestations in language, cultural norms, and power structures. Racism functions not as overt prejudice but as a systemic ideology embedded in cultural narratives, institutional procedures, and everyday discourse. Linguistic scientists highlight that language is considered as a tool for continuing racial hierarchies and a means for resistance, as racialized discourses normalize inequalities while marginalized societies recover terminology to maintain authority (Hill, 2008).

May (2023) defines racism as “acts and/or projects that use linguistic resources as a means of discrimination and subordination” (p.652). This definition emphasizes the active role of language in racism. In 2021, Merriam-Webster defines racism as “a belief that race is a fundamental determinant of human traits and capacities, and that racial differences produce an inherent superiority of a particular race.” It also includes behavior and attitudes that reflect and foster this belief, and more recently, “the systemic oppression of a racial group to the social, economic, and political advantage of another.” According to Baker-Bell (2020, p.20), linguistic racism can be illustrated as “the linguistic violence, dehumanization, persecution, and marginalization Black language-speakers endure when using their language across multiple contexts”. This definition states the linguistic injustice experienced by Black language speakers, emphasizing the harm and dehumanization that can stem from the devaluation of their language practices. Furthermore, Dovchin (2020) (as cited in May, 2023) and other resources represent

racism as a form of linguistic discrimination that signifies a “new racism, one which is essentially based on one’s language background, language practices, communicative properties”. Language is a key marker of racial discrimination in modern society. In 2019, according to the American Association of Biological Anthropologists (AABA), racism is “prejudice against someone because of their race and a belief in the inherent superiority and inferiority of different racial groups”. Racism is embedded in beliefs of racial order and is depicted through prejudice. Wellman (1993) presented racism as “culturally sanctioned beliefs, which, regardless of intentions included, defined the advantages whites have because of the subordinated position of racial sections”. This definition emphasizes the subtle and systematic methods through which racism functions via cultural norms and beliefs, perpetuating racial disparities.

The concept of race, the CATESOL Journal directly declares (2022) that “race is a social construct that has no basis in biological reality” (p.3). This definition highlights that race is not biologically inherent but socially constructed and maintained by means of cultural structures. The Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Classics in 2020 asserts that “since the late 20th century, race has been hugely regarded as a form of identity-based in social construction instead of biology”. This emphasized the importance of change in academic understanding over time. The American Anthropological Association (AAA), in its 2019 report, stated that “race does not provide an accurate representation of human biological variation. It was never accurate in the past, and it remains inaccurate when referencing the modern human population. Humans are not divided biologically into distinct continental types or racial genetic clusters”. This report from biological anthropologists emphasizes the scientific acceptance of the biological basis of race.

Another concept associated with race is racialization, which is defined by Leonardo (2024) as “the making of racialized groups,” beyond that clarifying it as “the process of dehumanizing people by categorizing them into racialized groups and distributing resources along racial lines”

(p.2). It highlights the active creation of racial categories and the inherent power imbalances associated with this process. Chun (2016) defined racialization as “the sociocultural processes through which race as an ideological dimension of human differentiation comes to be imagined, produced, and reified through language practices”. This definition emphasizes the essential role of language in making and enhancing racial categories. Also, Alim (2016) asserted that “language ideologies are inseparable from ideologies of race, suggesting that everyday linguistic interactions are inherently racialized and contribute to the reproduction of racial orders” (p.12). Eventually, Schmidt (2002) illustrates racialization as “a social process whose point is inequality, working by focusing specific groups as so foreign that they cannot be conceived as equal members of the same political community” (p.158). This definition highlights the function of racialization in producing political and social exclusion.

Another concept is ethnicity, which is recognized as including shared societal characteristics. John (2011, p.12), defines ethnicity as “a collectivity within a larger society having real or putative common ancestry, memories of a shared historical past, and a cultural focus on one or more symbolic elements defined as the epitome of their peoplehood”. This definition elucidates the shared cultural, history, and ancestry symbols that bind an ethnic group. Furthermore, Waters (1990), asserts that “people commonly associate ethnicity with distinctions based on national language, origin, religion, food, and other cultural markers, while connecting race to physical appearance” (p.400). This emphasizes the common comprehension of ethnicity as being rooted in societal practices and origins.

Racial discrimination is defined by Drozdowicz in (2024) as “a broad range of actions, experiences, practices which share a common core of an unfair treatment of a person based on their language”. He further clarifies that linguistic traits can act as a trigger for negative attitudes toward racial groups (P.3). This definition emphasizes the role of language in challenging racial

discrimination. Gannon (2016) asserts that racial discrimination is “any discrimination against any individual based on their ethnicity, race, ancestry or origin, and skin color or hair”. Discrimination happens when individuals exclude others from social interactions, business, and source sharing, drawing from group identity. As well as *Harvard Human Rights Journal* in 2020, explains racial discrimination as “any distinction, exclusion, restriction, or performance based on race color, descent, or national or ethnic origin which has the purpose or effect of nullifying or impairing the recognition, enjoyment, or exercise, on an equal footing, of human rights and fundamental freedoms in the political, economic, social, cultural, or any other field of public life” (p.2). This definition illustrates the complete nature of racial discrimination and its influence on human rights.

The concept of race originated in the early modern era, as a categorization of structurally modern humans (*Homo sapiens*) and has a widespread history in Europe and America (Kennedy, 2013). Historically, the modern word (race) was used in the sense of “ethnic group, nation” through the 6th to 19th centuries (Bancel, David, & Thomas, 2019, p.11). Race attained its modern meaning from the physical anthropology domain via scientific racism starting in the 9th century. In 2019, the American Association of Physical Anthropologists (AAPA) declared “the belief in ‘races’ as normal aspects of human biology, and the structures of inequality (racism) which arise from such beliefs, are among the most harmful elements in the human knowledge both historically and in contemporary times”. The word “race”, understood to mean an identifiable group of people who share common descent, was presented to English in the 16th century from the old French *rasse* in 1512, from Italian *razza* (Oxford University Press, 2024).

Race in sports media can enhance harmful patterns in the intellectual and athletic skills of distinct racial groups (Edmond, 2020). The concept of “platformed racism” has also emerged in the situation of sports games such as the FIFA series. Moreover, linguistic stereotypes in sports media coverage can show underlying racial biases (Srauy & Cheney-Lippold, 2019). The current

study intends to show the way race and its concepts are embedded to affect the uncovered discursive and linguistic strategies within sports reports.

2.4.1 Levels of Racism

A comprehensive contribution to recognizing the complexities of racism stems from the work of Dr. Camara Phyllis Jones (2008, pp.1212-1213), who suggested a recognized framework detailing three basic levels through which racism functions.

- 1- Institutional Racism:** is described as the differential access to the services, goods, and opportunities of a community by race. This form of racism is normalized, often legalized, and manifests as an inherited disadvantage. It is included within cultural structures, systematized in institutions of practice, customs, and law, such that a recognizable perpetrator is not always necessary for its perpetuation. Institutionalized racism can be noticed as inaction in response to the necessity. Its impact is in both material situations and access to power. Concerning material situations, an example encompasses disparities in access to quality education, sound cases, useful employment, suitable medical facilities, and a clean environment. With power, this level of racism manifests as distinctive access to information (involving one's history), resources (encompassing wealth and organizational framework), and voices (voting rights, representation in government, and control of media). The permanent association between socioeconomic status and race in various societies is a direct consequence of institutionalized racism, where historical injustices are sustained by modern structural factors.
- 2- Personally Mediated Racism:** is framed as prejudice and discrimination, where prejudice includes differential assumptions about the motives, abilities, and intentions of others based on their race, and discrimination indicates differential actions toward others according to

their race. This form of racism is most understood and comes to mind when “racism” is used. Personally mediated racism can be both intentional and unintentional, including acts of neglect. It is manifest in distinct ways, involving a lack of respect, suspension, and devaluation. While overt discriminatory actions and offensive language fall under this category, as well as it involves the more subtle ideologies and beliefs of individuals that find their way into policies and institutions, driving differential influence and access. This level emphasizes how individual biases and discriminatory behaviors denote the preservation of racial inequality in everyday communications.

- 3- Internalized Racism:** is the acceptance of individuals of marginalized races. It is used by a lack of belief in oneself and others who share their racial identity. Demonstration of internalized racism can involve the adoption of “whiteness” (utilizing hair smoothing tools or skin creams), self-devaluation (utilizing racial slurs as nicknames, refusing ancestral community), and feelings of quietness or helplessness. For example, a person of color may hate their skin color, or a native person may believe that native people are fundamentally less intelligent.

2.4.2 Critical Race Theory

CRT is “a collection of scholars and activists concerned with studying the relationship between racism, power, and race” (Delgado & Stefancic, 2001, p.2). CRT appeared in the mid-1970s when a group of activists, lawyers, and legal scholars throughout the United States separately understood that the important progress attained during the civil rights movement of the 1960s started to decline, and in some situations, was being reversed (Ansell, 2008). Walker (2015) claims that CRT emphasizes race as an element of inequality, highlights the influence of power dynamics in the framework of race and other interrelated social identities, questions the basis of

the cultural, liberal, and legal orders, and challenges the ideas of equality and naturality. Rabaka (2020) suggests that CRT provides scholars with critical and theoretical methods to analyze racism and race.

CRT is based on ideas from two distinct movements, Critical Legal Studies (CLS) and Radical Feminism, which influenced its development. It draws inspiration from the main European thinkers such as Antonio Gramsci and Jacques Derrida, as well as from American radical traditions depicted by Sojourner Truth, Frederick Douglass, and Du Bois. From CLS, the CRT adopted the concept of legal indeterminacy, which suggests that legal cases often lack a single, definitive outcome. Judges may decide cases in various ways, relying on which legal principles are highlighted or how facts are understood. From Radical Feminism, CRT unified the idea that power influences social roles and how they are sustained via hidden societal norms and everyday practices (Delgado & Stefancic, 2001).

CRT is based on three main principles and reinforced by two ideas that help to illustrate the way racism and race function within a community (Delgado & Stefancic, 2001).

First, the principle of “ordinaries” proposes that racism is a natural, everyday experience for people of color. Because racism is well established in the framework of legal and social systems, it is hard to illuminate. Legal approaches that focus on “color-blindness” treat anyone the same despite of their background (Delgado & Stefancic, 2001).

Second, the idea of “interest convergence” or “material discrimination” suggests that racism is still around because it functions in the interest of dominant groups. Both working-class and rich white individuals might be psychologically and materially from the sustained subordination of racial minorities (Delgado & Stefancic, 2001).

Third, CRT highlights the “social construction of race”, which states that race is not a fixed or biological reality but instead, a concept shaped and constructed by the community. However,

people might share particular physical features such as hair texture or skin color, such feature represents a minor aspect of their genetic configuration. Moreover, these features have no actual link to qualities like personality, intelligence, or morality (Delgado & Stefancic, 2001).

Strengthening these central levels, CRT presents two ideas: a “unique voice of color”, stating that individuals from marginalized groups, such as Indigenous, black, Asian, and Latino people, have respected viewpoints on race and racism that may not be available to their white counterparts. The “legal/counter storytelling” movement inspires writers from these groups to describe their personal experiences and views of racism and the legal system, giving exceptional insights that challenge typical legal narratives (Delgado & Stefancic, 2001).

In recent times, Bonilla-Silva (2015) developed the principle of CRT as follows: (a) Racism is well established in the structure of the community. (b) Racism has a “material foundation”. (c) Racism changes and evolves across different periods. (d) Racism is seen as reasonable. (e) Racism has modern foundations.

According to Kumaran (2023), CRT can be used in many ways, such as offering a framework to analyze any context based on a race-conscious perspective to comprehend racism, social justice, and inequality. It can be utilized as a metaphorical tool to analyze personal norms, existing norms, and historical norms, and provide radical perspectives and social criticism concerning deconstructing and reinterpreting.

2.5 Critical Discourse Analysis: An Overview

CDA, according to Van Dijk (1998), is a discourse analytical approach that uncovers how inequality, power abuse, and dominance are reproduced, resisted, and enacted through language in political and social contexts. There is a general understanding that CDA has historical roots originating from Greek philosophy.

Historically, the development of Discourse Analysis (DA), began with Chomsky's formal linguistic theories in the 1950s, which determined syntax and speaker competence while ignoring social aspects (Lyons, 1981; Hart, 2010). This language change and communication stereotypes led to the rise of Critical Linguistics (CL) in the late 1970s, where Kress and Hodge (1979) and Fowler (1979) linked linguistic analysis with power and ideological structures. CL developed into CDA, with Fairclough and Wodak (1997) extending its principles (Hart, 2010). Wodak (1995) highlighted the role of language in institutions and power dynamics, drawing from Halliday's SFL (Fairclough, 1992; Blommaert, 2005). By the close of the 1980s and early 1990s, scholars such as Van Dijk (1985), Fairclough (1989), and Wodak (1989) established CDA as a critical field that integrates language and social theory.

The development of DA has its roots in the rhetorical traditions of Greek sophists, who examined speech-making and persuasion in democratic communities (Johnstone, 2008). Marxist theories later proposed a focus on power and ideology, with Gramsci (1979) and Althusser (1971) indicating how ruling classes sustain dominance via repressive and ideological state devices (Jorgensen & Phillips, 2002; Fairclough, 2010). Habermas (1984) extended on these ideas by criticizing the systematic misrepresentation of communication in capitalist communities, asserting the "ideal speech situation" as a model for reasonable discourse (Fairclough & Wodak, as cited in Van Dijk, 1997). Foucault (2000) contested traditional Marxist ideology, examining discourse as a knowledge system that structures social institutions and power via mechanisms like confession and discipline (Fairclough, 1992; Wodak, 1996). Eventually, Bourdieu (1995) gave a sociological perspective, hypothesizing that power is distributed via social fields and different forms of capital (Coulthard, 1996). These contributions developed the foundations of contemporary DA, emphasizing the interplay between language, social structures, and power.

According to Richardson (2007), “The terms ‘discourse’ and ‘discourse analysis’ are challenged since their definitions extend beyond the domain of discourse studies itself” (p.21). According to Stubbs (1983), DA “is the study of language above the sentence or the clause. Therefore, its concern is the study of larger units, like interviews or long paragraphs” (p.1). Moreover, DA studies language use in interaction and social context among speakers (cited in Widdowson, 2004). Harris proposes that language can be structured as “connected discourse” (1952). He also asserts that DA is “clearly a set of procedures for establishing underlying formal equivalences within texts” (1952, p.3). Johnstone claims that DA differs from language analysis, which is not considered “an abstract system”, instead showing language as a way of communication to transmit knowledge in individuals' memories as they exchange information and express feelings (2003). McCarthy suggests that DA “is concerned with the analysis of printed and written texts as well as the analysis of spoken interaction” (1991, p.12). Consequently, it is not only above the sentence, in everyday life, individuals conduct language in hundreds of printed and written words; articles, stories, letters, and so on. Thus, discourse analysts are mainly interested in how written interactions are structured.

The foundations of CDA trace back to 1979 with the emergence of CL at the University of East Anglia, led by linguists such as Hodge, Fowler, and Kress (Kress & Hodge, 1979; Fowler, 1979). Fowler (1991,1996) later extended CL into linguistic criticism, approaching language as a socially included system that reflects ideological structures (Fairclough, 1989). Halliday’s SFL played an important role in influencing CL, highlighting language’s role in shaping knowledge, relationships, and social identities (Fairclough, 2010). Chomsky’s generative grammar, which emerged earlier, centered on language as a cognitive system, detached from social interactions (Fowler, 1991; Lyons,1981). CL corresponds to Halliday’s view of grammar as a framework of

social choice, which has been criticized for ignoring discourse as a site of social transformation and struggle (Fairclough, 1992).

Several scholars have provided definitions to illustrate the complexity of CDA. Al-Manaseer (2013) states that “CDA can be united by its critical focus on the ways in which knowledge, subjects, and power relations are produced, reproduced, and transformed within discourse” (2013, p.93). Van Dijk (2011) explains CDA as “discourse analytical research that basically studies the way social-power abuse and inequality are legitimized, enacted, resisted, and reproduced by text and talk in the political and social context” (p.466). CDA investigates how language usage may reproduce powerful ideologies, perspectives, and attitudes.

CDA, according to Baker & Ellece (2011), is:

An approach of discourse analysis, through which language is uncovered as a social practice since its concern is to investigate the ideologies and power, and how they are reflected via language. It aims to shape the ways discourse and language could maintain or resist oppressive practices (p.82).

Hart (2010) states that CDA is a theoretical approach that can analyze a wide range of linguistic patterns since it was initially developed from CL; therefore, it led to a variety of text types. CDA, according to Wodak & Mayer (2008), “considers power as a central concept because it scrutinizes the language of individuals who have more power and are responsible for social inequality” (p.9). Blommaret (2005) indicates that:

CDA differs from other approaches in that it highlights its critical nature on the way discourse, language, speech, and social hierarchy are interconnected. It analyzes the relations between social structures and discourse features; such relations are social problems like power relations, ideological effects, dominance, racism, and hegemony (p.25).

Wooffitt (2005) defines CDA as a method of text analysis that aims to reveal hidden ideologies that are grounded in texts instead of being directly expressed. Moreover, he points out that it seeks to uncover how political and social inequalities challenge and perpetuate in a community through language. Al-Manaseer (2013) declared that “CDA is not so much interested in language itself, but in the linguistic character of social and cultural processes and structures” (p.2). CDA is an academic interdisciplinary approach that represents both a method and a theory, and it differs from DA approaches in that it includes not only the interpretation and description of speech in context but also an account of how and why discourse functions. Scholars interested in this link between society and language have used CDA to assign them to explain, interpret, and understand such interaction. CDA is concerned with the way specific discourse patterns are used in the reproduction of social dominance, whether in news reports, conversations, or other genres (Rogers, 2004).

Fairclough and Wodak (1997, pp. 271-80) provide the following tenets of CDA:

- 1- CDA addresses social problems
- 2- Power relations are discursive
- 3- Discourse constitutes society and culture
- 4- Discourse does ideological work
- 5- Discourse is historical
- 6- The link between text and society is mediated
- 7- Discourse analysis is interpretative and explanatory
- 8- Discourse is a form of social action.

Practically, CDA serves as an alternative perspective that can be employed across various domains of linguistics. CDA can be integrated into distinct fields such as stylistics, sociolinguistics, pragmatics, narrative analysis, anthropology, and others. In addition, different approaches to CDA were developed by several scholars over time such as Michel Foucault (1972), Halliday and Hasan (1989), Van Dijk (1993), Norman Fairclough (1995), Ruth Wodak (2001), and Martin Reisigl and Ruth Wodak (2001), to analyze concepts such as, “power, ideology, class, gender, racism, dominance, hegemony, discrimination, interests, social order, social structure, reproduction, and institutions,” additional to the more common discourse-analytical concepts (Van Dijk, 1993, p.354).

2.6 Concepts Related to CDA

2.6.1 Ideology

According to Oxford Dictionary Websites, the word ideology means “a set of ideas that an economic or political system is based on, as well as a set of beliefs, especially one held by a particular group, that influences the way people behave”. The concept of Ideology was given by the French Philosopher Antoine Destutt de Tracy in 1796 as the “science of ideas” to develop a system of ideas to face the irrational impulses of the mob (Destutt, 1801).

Ideology, according to Mayer, is defined as:

A set of beliefs which are publicly expressed, to influence the orientation and action of others (1973, p.75). Mayer describes ideology as some intentions that could be considered legal, as they compose a set of beliefs of the people adopting them. It can be utilized to direct action to identify the intent as well as the range of an acceptable course of action to be taken (1982, p.15).

Ideology has offered characteristics, including being a set of values and a quality of an organization that is set to influence the actions of others, as well as relying on the goals of the organization.

Fairclough (1989, p.94), describes ideology as “ideas which arise from a given set of material interests”. Moreover, it is a kind of domination that is built on the unions, the interaction of minor groups, and the constant. In addition, ideology refers to the values, beliefs, or concepts that shape and influence how people or communities engage with the world. Sometimes these ideologies assume linguistic form and interfere in texts discreetly to reinforce or challenge a given society's principles and dynamics of power relations (Fairclough, 1995).

Van Dijk (2006) asserts that ideologies are often performed in media discourse on both the micro level of language through narrativity, vocabulary, and discursive construction of reality, and on the macro level through thematic and textual structures. According to him, ideologies are best associated with group interests and are most often patronizing to powerful groups to the detriment of the less powerful (2006). Looking for such ideologies is CDA’s challenge since its purpose is to raise awareness regarding the role they play in maintaining the existing social structures. Al-Manaseer (2013) states that “ideology is both a belief system and an idea that needs a cognitive element that has the ability to account properly for equally the notion of belief systems” (p.2). This study looks into ideology concerning racism in sports media reports. By exploring the language used in the reports, this study examines how racial ideologies are built and perpetuated or challenged in British and American sports media reports.

2.6.2 Power

Power is a central concept in CDA because it indicates how or through what individuals or groups dominate, control, or otherwise manage others, mainly through language. Fairclough (1995) defines power as “the ability acquired by dominant or influential groups or individuals that allows them to instill their political and social ideologies explicitly or implicitly via discourse” (p.1). In other words, it is how individuals get control and access to discourse via using various means for distributing, inspiring, and producing it. Rogers (2003) stated that power “is essential to show how power is generated, the role people play in that power structure, and what implications those lines of power have for consumers” (p.175). Lazar (2005, p.32) represents power as “the ability of a person to influence the behavior of others, it is managed as ‘a systematic characteristic’”. Van Dijk (2015) states that the notion of power is illustrated as defining social power in terms of control. Therefore, groups have (more or less) power if they are proficient to (more or less) controlling the minds and acts of (members of) other groups. This capability assumes a power base of advantaged access to limited social resources, such as money, force, status, knowledge, fame, or other forms of communication and public discourse.

Van Dijk (1996, p.84) suggests that power can be seen as:

groups have (more or less) power if they are able to (more or less) control the acts and minds of (members of) other groups. This ability presupposes a power base of privileged access to scarce social resources, such as force, money, status, fame, knowledge, information, "culture," or indeed various forms of public discourse and communication. The power of dominant groups may be integrated in laws, rules, norms, habits, and even a quite general consensus, and thus take the form of what Gramsci called "hegemony". Class domination, sexism, and racism are characteristic examples of such hegemony.

2.6.3 Dominance

Dominance refers to the maintained practice of power by one group over another, which leads to systematic disparities. Van Dijk (1993) defines dominance as “the exercise of social power by individuals, groups or institutions, which results in social inequality, encompassing cultural, ethnic, political, gender, and racial inequality” (249-250). Furthermore, Van Dijk (1996) explains it as an “immoral or illegal form of social power abuse” (p.84). Wodak declares that “CDA is interested in analyzing unclear and transparent structural relationships of dominance, power, discrimination, and control as manifest in language” (1995, p.204). Dominant leaders (Baker & Ellece, 2011) may persuade dominated people to the degree that they trust that their status is natural and authentic by blinding them from the truth of their intentions.

Van Dijk (1996, p.85) argues that dominance can be seen as:

A form of power abuse that can be found in breaks of principles, rules, and laws of justice, equality, and democracy of powerful people. Hence, it lacks any acceptable or legitimate fundamentals. It may emerge essentially in advanced economic cultures that aim to establish variant means of clarifying the imbalanced distribution of resources to maintain the social hierarchies of specific groups.

This study emphasizes the significance of uncovering how dominance is sustained linguistically. By exploring these patterns, CDA aims to maintain and challenge unequal power relations embedded in discourse.

2.6.4 Hegemony

According to Gramsci, hegemony is derived from the work of Antonio Gramsci as a concept that depicts a strategy that dominates organizations to achieve the consent of subordinated

groups in order not to exploit their dominance through force (1971). Fairclough (1992) assumes that hegemony can be understood as:

The power over society as a whole is about shaping unions and integrating instead of dominating and controlling minor classes, via ideological or business ways to in their mutual understanding. He claims that it is never employed to use an absolute or eternal force. However, it is argued that mental control can affect the attitudes of people (p.92).

Fairclough (2003) describes hegemony as “a way of theorizing power and the struggle for it in industrial communities, which poses how power relies on acceptance or agreement instead of just force and the importance of ideology” (218). Therefore, discourse can be seen as a tool to receive hegemonic struggle and hegemony. Bloomeart (2005) describes hegemony as “dominant and determining factors in ideological processes which detect the reproduction of dominant culture as the ‘coercive and dispelling system of education’” (p.167).

2.6.5 Critique

Fairclough (2001) asserts that “CDA is ‘critical’ because it targets language and its relation to the community” (p.133). According to Breez (2011), “the origins of CDA that tackles issues like the relation between society and politics may have originated from the authors who sustained thoughts related to Marxism. CDA is associated with the Frankfurt school whose members were interested in Marxism’s focus on ‘capitalism’ in the 20th century” (p.496). The common point between the Marxist theory and CDA is that both of them are critical; because the Marxists aimed to “judge and prescribe” in the time when most other social scholars trusted that their purpose was to “observe and interpret” (Breez, 2011).

Wodak (2001) argues that critique “is a systematic and reflective process of analyzing and evaluating discourses, practices, and cultural artifacts to uncover and manifest the primary power ideologies, structures, and social inequalities that they sustain” (p.5).

2.7 Approaches of CDA

Various approaches to CDA have been developed in response to the many beliefs held by DA scholars, and they are presented in different ways. The more widely accepted and established approaches include those of Norman Fairclough’s (1989, 2001) approach, Van Dijk’s (1993) approach, and Ruth Wodak’s (2001) approach, as well as Halliday and Matthiessen’s (2014) SFL approach is also used as a linguistic toolkit within CDA studies. Which are presented in details in the next section.

2.7.1 Fairclough’s Three-Dimensional Approach

Norman Fairclough’s approach to CDA is one of the fundamental frameworks for recognizing how language operates within social power structures. Fairclough (1989) represented his approach to language and discourse in *Critical Language Study*, illustrating the aims of this approach as “a contribution to the general rising of consciousness of exploitative social relations, through focusing upon language” (p.4). Such aims endure in his later developments that enhance his approach to becoming one of the most influential frameworks of CDA (Fairclough, 1995). This section provides a general overview of Fairclough’s work on CDA. According to Chuliaraki and Fairclough (1999), CDA will be acknowledged for “bringing social science and linguistics together within a single analytical and theoretical framework, setting up a dialogue between them” (p.6). The mentioned linguistic theory denotes SFL, which is considered the basis for Fairclough’s

analytical framework (Fowler, 1991). The approach of Fairclough builds upon some critical social theorists, such as Foucault (concept of orders of discourse), Gramsci (concept of hegemony), Habermas (concept of colonization of discourses), and others (Fairclough, 1989, 1995). Fairclough (1995, p.132) defines CDA as:

A form of discourse analysis that aims to systematically explore often opaque relationships of causality and determination between (a) discursive practices, events, and texts, and (b) wider social and cultural structures, relations, and processes. It investigates how such practices, events, and texts arise out of and are ideologically shaped by relations of power and struggles over power, and further, explores how the opacity of these relationships between discourse and society is itself a factor securing power and hegemony.

For Fairclough (1995), there are three basic analytical focuses in analyzing any communicative event through CDA. Including text analysis (description stage), discourse practice (interpretation stage), and sociocultural practice (explanation stage).

Firstly, “text” is the main analytical focus of Fairclough’s three-dimensional approach. Analysis of text encompasses Linguistic Analysis (LA) such as (grammar, vocabulary, semantics, phonetics and phonology, and syntax). LA is employed for to text’s semantic and lexical-grammatical aspects, which have mutual influence on each other (Fairclough, 1995). Following SFL, Fairclough reveals text from a multifunctional viewpoint. Accordingly, any sentence in a text can be analyzed in terms of the comprehension of these functions, which are labeled by him as “relations, identities, and representations” (Fairclough, 1995, pp.57-58).

Secondly, “discursive practice” includes two aspects: “institutional process (editorial procedures), and discourse process (e.g., production and consumption)” (Fairclough, 1995, p.59). Discourse practice revolves around “the division between culture and society on the one hand,

language, text, and discourse on the other” (Fairclough, 1995, p.60). The figure below presents Fairclough's analysis levels.

Figure 1

CDA Framework of Communicative Events

Note. Adopted from Fairclough (1995, p.59).

In Fairclough’s analytical framework, there are two linguistic levels of analysis, namely, the text level and discourse level, which Fairclough calls “intertextual analysis” (1995, p.61). Intertextual analysis “focuses on the borderline between discourse practice and text in the analytical framework (Fairclough, 1995, p.16). Fairclough describes intertextuality as “basically the property texts have of being full of grabs of other texts, which may be directly merged or demarcated in, and which the text may assimilate, ironically echo, and contradict” (1992, p.84).

Thirdly, “sociocultural practice”, following Fairclough's framework (1995), the analysis for this dimension focuses on three aspects: “economic (e.g., the economy of media), political (e.g. ideology and power of media), and cultural (e.g., issues of values)” As Fairclough (1995) asserted that, “there are many participants and groups who do not access to mass media equally with regard

to broadcasting, writing, and speaking. He confirms that this is because media productivity is under institutional and professional control, and it is generally for those who have cultural, economic, and political power, who have crucial access to media” (p.40).

Table 1

Fairclough’s CDA Framework

Item No.	Description	Interpretation	Explanation
1	Vocabulary Context	Situational Context Intertextuality	Social Determinants
2	Grammar Text	Vocabulary, phonology, and grammar Meaning of Utterance Local Coherence	Ideologies
3	Text Structure	Topic and Point	Effects

Note. Adopted from Fairclough (1989, pp. 109- 168)

Fairclough’s three-dimensional framework suggests that each discursive event is seen as having three stages; in the descriptive stage, which focuses on analyzing (vocabulary, grammar, and text structure). The interpretative stage mainly includes understanding the context (situational and intertextuality) and the text (vocabulary, phonology, grammar, meaning of utterance, local coherence, and topic and point). The last stage of the explanation explores broader social factors involving (social determinants, ideologies, and effects). This three-dimensional framework is basic for understanding how language enhances power structures in society.

In sum, CDA, summarized by practitioners (Van Dijk, 1998; Wodak, 1996; Fairclough, 1995; Hodge & Kress, 1993; Kress, 1991) as follows:

- 1- Language is a social practice that depicts the world.
- 2- Discourse serves as a social practice for constructing and representing social actions (e.g., domination, power, resistance).
- 3- Texts originate meanings from the interaction between social participants (readers and writers) and texts.
- 4- Linguistic structures and features are important, whether uncountably or concisely conducted.
- 5- Power relations are maintained, practiced, and constructed via discourse.
- 6- Writers and speakers work from certain discursive practices impacted by their interests, which include inclusion and exclusion.
- 7- CDA can function both to explain and interpret texts.

2.7.2 Van Dijk's Socio-Cognitive Approach

Van Dijk is one of the most referenced approaches in critical studies of media discourse, and in studies that do not mainly fit within CDA studies (Ezewudo, 1998; Karim, 2000). In the 1980s, he primarily established his discourse analysis theory in media texts concerning the representation of ethnic groups and minorities in Europe. In his *News Analysis* (1988), he applied his general theory of discourse to news discourse in the press and employed his theory to authentic cases of news reports for both international and national levels. According to Hart (2015), the Socio-Cognitive Model (SCM) was developed by Van Dijk to “provide a model that connects social, textual, and cognitive structures. This model functions to include discursive structures of

social inequality, through which, cognition mediates between society and text” (p.15). As noted by Van Dijk (1998, 2000, 2008) social cognition mediates textual and social structures. For him (1998), social cognition is a “system of social processes and mental representations of group participants in specific contexts” (p.47). This model deals with issues related to ideology because it explores the way ideologies control social practices in society (Van Dijk, 1998).

Van Dijk (1980) developed a theory named Semantic Macrostructure, which includes macro and micro levels of discourse. The macrostructure concept fundamentally revolves around Thematic Structure in news discourse. Through which topics are structured and organized to encompass an overview of news discourse. Macro-Level (macrostructure) involves both “schematic structure” which is associated with the organized structures of the topics involved in the news discourse, and “thematic structure” which revolves around two crucial aspects: *proposition* defined by Van Dijk (1988) as “the smallest independent meaning constructs of language and thought” (p.31). *Macroproposition* is defined as the “overall topic or theme which indicates a global meaning to a sentence, paragraph, or a whole text” (1988). while Micro-Level (microstructure) according to Van Dijk (1988) involves *specifications* that contain “the level of precision or detail used to describe actions, people, and events in a discourse.” (p.111) *Local coherence* “refers to the rational connection between sentence or propositions. It confirms that each part of a text should make sense” (p.49). *Implications* are “implicit meanings that listeners or readers can infer from the discourse” (p.19). *Lexical style* includes “the choice of vocabulary, which can carry ideology, bias, or attitudes, i.e., words can charge informal or formal” (p.24). *Syntactic style* focuses on “the structure of the sentences, such as clause complexity, active and passive voice, and sentence length” (p.28). Finally, *rhetoric* revolves around “the use of stylistic and persuasive devices such as repetition, metaphors, hyperbole, or euphemism” (p.178). The following figure shows the components of the semantic macrostructure

Figure 2

The Components of Semantic Macro Structure

Note. Components of Semantic Macrostructure by Van Dijk (1980, 1988, 1991, 1997)

In relevance to Van Dijk, the CDA approach is a multidisciplinary approach. In his earlier work, *Racism and Press* (1991), Van Dijk argues that there are five requirements to state a multidisciplinary approach and to explore the representation of ethnic minorities in the press. First, a socio-political analysis is conducted to explore the role the press plays in reducing racism. Second, contemporary research on how discourse is employed and organized is the basis for analyzing news reports. Third, recognizing and memorizing the news discourse involves a topic that requires an account of cognitive psychology. Fourth, changing and forming attitudes, beliefs, or ideologies should be interpreted in a new framework of communication and social cognition. Fifth, the embodiment of the aforementioned requirements within a comprehensive framework to uncover racism in social sciences (Van Dijk, 1991). This multidisciplinary approach is coherent since it is described by a comprehensive DA.

Van Dijk's (1998, 2000) theory of ideology, known as the Ideological Square, is presented as "the basic social representations of the beliefs shared by group members. They serve as the framework that illustrates the overall coherence of these beliefs" (p.14). Van Dijk (2000) realizes ideologies as they interact between cognition and social structure (discourse). CDA is defined by Van Dijk (2001) as:

A type of discourse analytical research that studies the way social power, abuse, dominance, and inequality are resisted, enacted, and reproduced by talk and text in the political and social contexts. With each research critical discourse analysis serves an explicit position, and thus wants to expose, understand, and resist social inequality (p.352).

Van Dijk's (2000, p.44) "ideological square" involves four principles:

- (1) Emphasize positive things about Us, (2) Emphasize negative things about Them,
- (3) De-emphasize negative things about Us, and (4) De-emphasize positive things about Them.

This ideological square is understood as the strategy of positive self-presentation or face-keeping when stating the in-group members, and negative other-presentation when stating the out-group members. As noted by Van Dijk (2015, p.64), his sociocognitive framework of CDA is categorized by a Discourse-Cognition-Society triangle. This triangle contains three related components that facilitate interaction between discourse and society. First is the cognitive component, which is associated with memory and the mind. Second, there is the social component, which focuses on “the organizations that explicitly or implicitly control public discourse” (p.70). Third, the discourse component remains the main component of CDA; within it, CDA does not focus on discourse structure, instead, it makes use of the aforementioned components. Van Dijk states that these components concentrate on “explaining and describing the way discourse may be included in the (re)production of power abuse, and how the role of attitude, knowledge, and ideologies in such discursive domination is maintained” (2015, p.72). The figure below reveals the relationship between the triangle’s components.

Figure 3

Socio-Cognitive Approach

Note. The Approach Related to Van Dijk (2015)

2.7.3 Wodak's Discourse Historical Approach

Wodak (1995) developed an approach named the Discourse-Historical Approach (DHA), which realizes both spoken and written forms of language as a social practice. Moreover, the DHA attempts “to integrate systematically all existing background information in the interpretation and analysis of various layers of spoken or written text” (p.209). Fairclough and Wodak (1997, p.258) argued that “language as a social practice”. includes discursive and non-discursive social practices that are formed by them. They adopt a dialectal connection between specific discursive practices and certain fields of action (social structures, situations, and institutional frames), where the first part (discourse) of this connection, influences the second one, in turn, the second part (social structures, situations, and institutional frames) shapes and affects the first (discourse) (1997). Moreover, in stating her approach to CDA, Wodak (2000) suggests that “her approach attempts to incorporate the historical source and background knowledge of the political and social texts or topics to analyze and explore the discursive event by interpreting the historical changes in discourse genres. She presents an explanation for the term ‘context’ by combining different social theories” (p.187).

The DHA is tied to the CDA and stands for the orientation of the socio-philosophy of critical theory. It traces a combination of social critique that includes three interrelated aspects. One is related to the dimension of action, and the others are related to the cognition dimension. This group of critical types of discourse includes: (a) discourse inherently critique, (b) socio-diagnostic critique, and (c) prognostic critique (Wodak & Mayer, 2001). They can be illustrated as:

- 1- Discourse or text critique stands for exploring the inconsistencies, (self) self-contradiction, dilemmas, and paradoxes in the discourse or text's internal structures.

2- The socio-diagnostic critique is associated with the demystifying exposure of the possibly manipulative or persuasive character of discourse practices.

3- The prognostic critique concerns the improvement and transformation of communication.

The triangulation approach (2001) is based on “the idea of ‘context’ which revolves around five levels, namely, the linguistic co-text level, the intertextual level, the extralinguistic level, the sociopolitical level and the historical context level” (p.67).

Weiss and Wodak (2003) recognize CDA as a transdisciplinary approach since it needs an ideal integration of theoretical approaches, which results in new, complete approaches. This integration may encompass various levels in both the application of the work and the suggested theory. Such a form of integration can be utilized to understand different subjects within a framework of transdisciplinary or interdisciplinary approaches (2003). Knapp and Landweer (1995) state five arguments that clarify the presence of interdisciplinary work in CDA:

- 1- Historical argument: Complex issues like racism and identity cannot be stated by a single discipline; they need interdisciplinary approaches.
- 2- Sociological arguments: Job markets and competition drive traditional academic progress, fail to state issues in institutional structures, and education.
- 3- Epistemological argument: Traditional procedures of theory and data collection create obstacles to knowledge creation and gaining new ways of thinking.
- 4- Content-based argument: The increasing difficulty of social relations needs a return to integrate insights from multiple disciplines.
- 5- Political argument: Forming a new way of thinking requires critical thinking and interdisciplinary integration.

2.8 Halliday's Systemic Functional Linguistic Approach

M.A.K. Halliday developed SFL as an approach to language during the 1960s in the United Kingdom and Australia (O'Donnell, 2012). SFL is based on the previous works of certain linguists, such as J.R. Firth and Bronislaw Malinowski. He (O'Donnell, 2012) developed the theory of Malinowski, emphasizing the centrality of situational context, and applied it through his linguistic model. In addition, Halliday (1960) developed an approach to phonology called "prosodic phonology", which enables phonological features to be shared over successive phonemes instead of each phoneme having its unique features (p.6).

SFL is characterized by distinct features in comparison with other linguistic systems. The SFL was developed by Michael Halliday, and transformational generative grammar was developed by Noam Chomsky have been considered two significant and influential traditions in the linguistic field (Halliday & Matthiessen, 1997). Halliday believes that linguistics should state actual sentences with various functions and without deep structure, i.e., he was concerned with the function of the sentence or the purpose of the writer in writing the sentence. However, Chomsky asserted that linguistics should go beyond just stating syntactic structures and aim to illustrate why language is structured.

Practically, the SFL approach is used worldwide, specifically in DA, semantics, and other approaches such as language education. It is closely associated with sociology, still when numerous linguistic theories address language in the form of mental practice (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014). Halliday is concerned with the manner in which language is employed in social settings to attain a particular target (O'Donnell, 2012).

SFL is widely regarded as an "applicable linguistic theory", which is used to be applied to solve problems that emerge through global communities (Halliday & Matthiessen, 1997). Halliday (2008) argues that his goal is to create a coherent tradition of language that is concerned with

applicable theory that would be crucial for several researchers. SFL is significant and can be employed in various fields such as education, computational linguistics, translation, and other newly discovered fields of application (Matthiessen, 2010). SFL has been helpful and widely used in pivotal fields such as educational linguistics (Christie & Martin, 1997), linguistic education (Christie & Martin, 1997), child language development (Painter, 1999), administrative language (Iedema, 2003), media discourse (Iedema, 2003), history (Iedema, 2003), and critical discourse analysis (Bloor & Bloor, 2007). Moreover, it has been utilized to analyze the grammar of other semiotic modes, like art (Ballantyre, 1996) and visuals (Kress & Leeuwen, 2001).

According to SFL, text can be analyzed in four ways: (a) context, (b) semantics, (c) phonology, and (d) lexico-grammar. As shown in the figure below:

Figure 4

Strata of SFL

Note. SFL Strata Adopted from Halliday (1976)

Context is categorized as one of the crucial aspects that is fundamental to the overall process of making meaning. It is worth noting that, when language occurs in a context, it will relate to many contexts (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014), such as the context of culture and the context of the situation. Halliday illustrates the context of the situation by stating the way distinct parts of the context are linked to the language employed in the text, he states this employment in three parts: Field, tenor, and mode. The first level of context of the situation is the Field, which gives an implication of the topic or what is being talked about. Secondly, Tenor gives an implication of who is/are involved in the communication and the relationships between them. Thirdly, Mode gives an implication of what aspect of language is applying to the interaction and which form (spoken/written) it takes. Such levels are described to illustrate people's comprehension through which individuals utilize different resources, kinds, and parts from the language system (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014). In stating "a language-based theory of learning," Halliday (1993, p.93) states how language attains three functions in creating meaning:

2.8.1 The ideational metafunction: Constructs experiences and ideas by the use of 'field' resources. As viewed below in Table 2, such resources create patterns of transitivity, which encompass the selection of particular types of verbs (processes). These types of verbs create functionally various types of nouns and noun groups (participants). Additionally, different types of adverbs and propositional phrases create different types of (circumstances) associated with place, time, and manner (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014). The next table shows the details of the field resources:

Table 2*Process and Participant Type*

Process type	Examples	Transitivity and participant role		
Material	Give, make, destroy	<u>Jules</u> picked up <u>the prescription</u> for <u>her mom</u> .	Actor	goal beneficiary
Verbal	Whisper, say, scream	<u>The teacher</u> announced <u>a test</u> .	Sayer	verbiage
Mental	Love, believe	<u>Anna</u> wanted to go for a <u>long run</u> .	Senser	phenomenon
Behavioural	Lough, watch, listen	<u>Erica</u> watches late-night TV.	Behavior	
Relational	Seem, be, have	<u>Jesse</u> is a really <u>nice guy</u> .	Carrier	attribute
Existential	Remain, be, exist	There is <u>empty space between molecules in a gas</u> .	existent	

2.8.2 The interpersonal metafunction: Creates interpersonal dynamics, which involve creating degrees of formality and familiarity and power dynamics by using ‘tenor’ resources, which involve mood, modality, and appraisal systems. The mood of the system, as viewed in Table 3, encompasses methods for making statements by utilizing the declarative mood, asking questions through the interrogative mood, or giving commands through the imperative mood (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014). The following table provides an overview of tenor resources:

Table 3*The Mood System*

Mood	Function	Example	Speech role
Declarative	For making statements	The player assisted in a goal.	Giving information
Interrogative	For asking questions	Did the player assist a goal?	Requesting information
Imperative	For giving commands or requests	Kick the ball!	Demanding an action

The mood system is crucial for interpersonal metafunction in how language is constructed. It gives choices to: give information, ask for information, and give commands or requests. The interpersonal metafunction focuses on the way language is utilized to interact with others, establish power dynamics, express judgments, attitudes, and create relationships. As it demonstrates the interaction tenor, who is speaking, with what authority, to whom, and with what degree of formality?

The system of tenor also involves resources of modality to create the certainty or possibility degrees. As demonstrated in Table 4, certainty degrees can be expressed by means of modal verbs (may, might, could, should, will, must) which express degrees of possibility, necessity, and obligation, modal nouns (possibility, probability, certainty, obligation) nominalize modality to state emphasis or formality, and modal adverbs (probably, perhaps, possibly, certainly, absolutely) to modify statements and show confidence or doubt (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014). The following table summarizes the resources of modality:

Table 4*The Modality System*

Modality type	Resource	Examples	Function
Modal verbs	Modal/auxiliary verbs	may, might, could, should, will, must	Stating degrees of possibility, necessity, and obligation.
Modal nouns	Nouns Convey Modality	possibility, probability, certainty, obligation	Nominalize modality to state emphasis or formality
Modal adverbs	Adverbs stating certainty	probably, perhaps, possibly, certainly, absolutely	Modify statements and show confidence or doubt

Derwianka and Jones (2016) declare that language users do not easily change the commands, questions, statements, and offers modality system. Instead, they also adjust the strengths, express attitudes, and engage the reader or listener via the semiotic choices they make. Accordingly, the interpersonal metafunction implies the appraisal system, which is described by (White and Martin, 2005), offering resources for the expression of attitude, engagement, and graduation. Attitude shows personal feelings, judging the actions of people or moral character, and evaluating the quality of something. Engagement offers agreeing or disagreeing with the reader/listener or other views, while Gradation gives choices for adjusting the interpersonal force of the message (Halliday, 1960). The next table shows the main points of the appraisal system:

Table 5*Appraisal System*

Aspect	Function	Examples	Purpose
Attitude	Expresses emotions, judgment, and evaluations	Sad, happy Fair, honest Bad decision	For expressing personal feelings or moral evaluations
Engagement	Stating viewpoints or other voices	It looks that... According to scholars.. It is worth noting ..	For agreeing or disagreeing with the reader/listener or other views
Graduation	Modifies the force or passion	True qualified So good	For adjusting the strength of the expressions

2.8.3 The textual metafunction: In SFL, the textual metafunction is concerned with the way language structures ideas to create connected and coherent texts (Derwianka and Jones, 2016). It deals with the flow of information through *theme/rheme structures*, *cohesive devices* (e.g., repetition, pronouns, and synonyms), and *logical connectors*. The notion of *theme* concentrates on presenting given or known information at the beginning of the clause; *rheme*, on the other hand, focuses on adding new information (Halliday & Matthiessen, 2014). There are five central theme/rheme patterns in textual metafunction:

- 1- **Constant Theme:** The same theme will be repeated via sentences to maintain the topic.
- 2- **Zigzag Pattern:** The new information (rheme) of one sentence, as stated by Eggins (2004), becomes the given information of the next (theme).
- 3- **Time and Place:** Using words such as (later, yesterday, in 1980) to indicate a historical or event topic.
- 4- **Interpersonal Themes:** Starting with the feelings or judgment of the writer to demonstrate their stance or attitude.

5- Textual Themes: Using connecting words (then, however, yet) to link clear ideas.

Table 6

Theme/Rheme Patterns in Textual Metafunction

Pattern type	Focus	Examples	Function
Constant theme	Same topic or theme sustained via various sentences.	My cat loves me. My cat eats a lot. My cat sleeps at night.	Through the whole paragraph, the focus is on one topic.
Zigzag pattern	The new information (rheme) of one sentence becomes the given information of the next (theme).	Sam saw a dog on the roof. The dog was chasing a cat. The cat ate a fish. The fish was big.	Constructs a clear and connected chain of ideas.
Time and place themes	Themes focus on when or where something happened.	Sam had work yesterday. Later, he met his friend in the park.	Uncovers when or where events happened in history or a story.
Interpersonal themes	Sentences start with the attitudes, feelings, or evaluations of the speaker.	Sadly, the food was not good. Sam feels happy today. The player is professional.	Shares the views and emotions of the writer.
Textual themes	Words or phrases that connect paragraphs or clauses and draw attention to the reader.	First, I visited my friend. Then, we played together. Finally, we went home.	Organize the writing and make it logical.

Note. This table illustrates the main points of theme/rheme patterns.

Figure 5*Text and Context Dynamics*

Note. The Dynamics related to Halliday (1960-1970).

2.9 Previous Studies

In this section, a list of previous studies that are relevant to the current study will be reviewed chronologically. These studies contribute to determining the theoretical foundation and revealing the current methodology.

The first study is entitled “A Comparative Study of After-Match Reports of ‘Lost’ and ‘Won’ Football Games within the Frameworks of Critical Discourse Analysis”, by Behnam and Jahanban (2015). It explored how language is utilized in after-match reports to influence the perceptions of the football teams. This study used the CDA approach based on Hodge and Kress’s (1996) model. Four reports from Manchester United’s website, two for winning games and two for losing games, were analyzed. Their analysis tackled the linguistic features such as grammatical

aspects, vocabulary choices, and rhetorical strategies. The study concluded that reporters, whether consciously or unconsciously, highlight their team's strength in victory while, in defeat, downplay weaknesses, they focus on their team's actions instead of the outcomes.

The second study is entitled "Critical Discourse Analysis of Football Reports: The Case Study of Real Madrid Official Website", by Rahimi and Sahragard (2017). It examined the way linguistic strategies in online match reports reflect fundamental ideologies. By conducting the CDA approach, the researchers explored four reports from Real Madrid's official Website, two losses and two wins from La Liga and the Champions League 2016-2017 season. Applying Fairclough's framework and Hodge and Kress's syntagmatic model for linguistic analysis. The analysis uncovered how Real Madrid was depicted more favorably by media reports, highlighting their strengths and downplaying losses, through attributive description, vocabulary, and transitivity. Moreover, the findings stated that even official reports can be affected by judgments.

The third study is entitled "A Discourse Analysis of Selected Football Texts", by Olagunju (2019). It examined the linguistic features of football reporting in Nigerian newspapers. Applying the Generic Structural Potential framework by Ansary and Babai (2005), and the approach is SFL, the study analyzed 13 articles from the "Complete Sports" newspapers during the 2010 World Cup. The data explored the structural elements within the context of football reporting, uncovering how these elements contribute to the overall text of social function and meaning. The study concludes that the Generic Structural Potential framework effectively uncovers the contextual and discourse structures of football texts, illustrating how particular linguistic choices reveal the social and communicative aims of sports journalism.

The fourth study is entitled "Critical Discourse Analysis on Representation of Racism and Solidarity in Adidas's Tweets", by Indrawati (2021). It examined how Adidas uses Twitter to

convey messages about racism and solidarity. The data involved 12 tweets from the official account of Adidas. The study concluded that Adidas influences humanitarian and declarative statement themes to represent direct support for the Black community, employees, and the Black Lives Matter movement, illustrating a commitment to combating racism and promoting solidarity.

The fifth study is entitled “The Language of Football: A Critical Discourse Analysis of The FIFA World Cup 2022 Social Media Coverage”, by Ghaffori (2023). It was carried out via the CDA approach, adopting Van Dijk’s socio-cognitive model, to explore how international media depict the 2022 FIFA World Cup, which was hosted by Qatar. The data involved five reports chosen from BBC News and YouTube channels, concentrating on negative portrayals of the event. The study concluded that the Arab Muslim world was depicted as repressive and deemphasized its values, utilizing the World Cup as a platform to foster negative ideologies.

The sixth study is entitled “Discourse Structure of the Sports Reports of the 2022 FIFA World Cup in Kenyan Newspapers”, by Wekesa and Ong’onda (2023). The study was carried out via the CDA approach based on Van Dijk and Fairclough's models. The researchers analyzed 62 news reports of the World Cup football from Kenyan newspapers on 20th November and 20th December of 2022. They explored the structure of these reports, concentrating on the main events, headlines, and leads to comprehend the way language is utilized to depict football discourse. This study concluded that such news reports track a particular structure and use linguistic devices, involving connotative headlines, vivid descriptions, and summarizing leads, frequently applying war metaphors, to convey information and engage readers.

The seventh study is entitled “Hate Speech and Racism in Sports Media: Analytical Study in Sports News in Social Media Networks”, by Makki (2023). It examined the raised problem of discriminatory and racist discourse within sports media, specifically on social media. By applying

the mixed-methods approach merging case study and content analysis, the study explored 40 instances of racist abuse on specific platforms such as TikTok and Twitter during basic events in Europe in 2019 and 2022. The data analysis revealed an important widespread presence of motivated hate speech, traced by racially charged abuse, by targeting players due to their ethnicity, disability, or religion. The study concluded that there is a gap in the growing widespread presence of online platforms, and it emphasizes the need for tougher action from governing bodies and sports media platforms to combat this issue.

The eighth study is entitled “Contrasting Media Representation of Race and National Identity: The Case of England and Italy at the Union of European Football Association Euro 2020”, by Mauro (2024). The study applied the CDA approach to explore how national identity and race were depicted in the print media coverage of the final Euro 2020 between Italy and England. The study analyzed articles and images from the British “Daily Mail” newspapers and the Italian “Corriere della Sera” newspapers, focusing on the contrasting representations of the teams. The findings showed differing discourses on race and nationhood, impacted by each socio-political context and immigration narratives, emphasizing the role of the media as gatekeepers of national identity.

The ninth study is entitled “The Construction of the Perfect Message in a Digital Environment: The Case of Vinicius Junior and Racism”, by Casado-Linares (2025). The qualitative approach focused on analyzing the 50 most liked comments from the panel discussion concerning Vinicius Junior’s denunciation of racism in Spanish football. The study uncovered those empathetic messages can have an important impact, specifically when they interact with a dual argument that allows opposite views. This underscored the multifaceted processes of online discourse and the efficiency of well-structured arguments.

Simultaneously, the studies have significantly contributed to the understanding of media, racism, and representation, and the current study makes an important contribution to the same concepts. Various studies have explored racism in football media in a generic or a specific region. Conversely, this study focuses on the coverage of the Ballon d'Or award, specifically in 2024, and the media reports surrounding the exclusion of Vini Jr. Moreover, it encompasses sports reports through both British and American journals, providing a better view of racial discourse in football narratives. Contrary to some quantitative studies, this study is based on a case study design and employs a qualitative approach. It highlights the deeper, more context-sensitive explanation for the way racism is constructed and shaped linguistically in particular media texts. Furthermore, these elements collectively ensure that the study contributes new, valuable insights to the growing literature on racism, sports reports, and media.

Chapter Three

Methodology

3.0 Introduction

This chapter provides a comprehensive discussion of the research methodology used in this study. It states the key elements of the research in detail, such as the research design, data collection and analysis procedures, followed by the analytical framework, as well as validity and reliability, in addition to the ethical considerations.

3.1 Research Design

Research design, as stated by Corbin (1997), is a procedural and strategic framework that might be followed to determine the required methods for a research topic. The focus of the framework is to assign the specified data collection procedures and the rules outlined to ensure a methodical system of collection. Denzin and Lincoln (2011) state that research designs of inquiry include quantitative, qualitative, and mixed methods approaches that state a particular way for procedures in a research study (strategy of inquiry). The current study is carried out through the qualitative research approach. Creswell (2018) defines qualitative research as “a means of exploring and understanding the meaning individuals or groups ascribe to a social or human problem. The process of research includes emerging questions and procedures, as well as collecting and analyzing data inductively” (p.380). A specific inquiry design is adopted for this

study, framed as a case study, which Creswell (2018) describes as, “a design of inquiry found in many fields, especially evaluation, in which the researcher develops an in-depth analysis of a case, often a program, event, activity, process, or one or more individuals” (p.15).

Additionally, the current study is conducted through a content analysis approach. White and Marsh (2006) state that content analysis is “a method which is employed qualitatively or quantitatively for methodically analyzing written, visual, or verbal documentation” (p.22). Neuman (1997) believes that content analysis is “a technique for analyzing and gathering the content of the text (words, pictures, meanings, ideas, themes, symbols, or any messages that can be conveyed)” (p.237).

3.2 Data Collection

Data collection in the current study is based on particular criteria that have been taken into account. CDA does not present a specific method for data collection; rather, the collection of data depends on the aims of the study. Fairclough (2005) confirms that the choice of suitable methods (data collection, selection, and analysis) depends on the study objectives. Polkinghorne (2005) implies that data functions as the ground through which the findings are constructed.

Specifically, the data of the current study involve four recognized media outlets, two British and two American. The British journals include the BBC and the Guardian, while the American journals include the New York Times and ESPN. Within each journal, two reports are selected, and

for each report, two extracts are analyzed, and the total number of extracts is 16 extracts. These texts are selected based on their relevance to the study. The process of data collection is not instantaneous; it has required constant manual review and searching. A personal effort was made and took many weeks to find reports that primarily address racism, race, or stereotypical framing concerning Vini Jr. and his exclusion from the Ballon d'Or award 2024.

The criteria for data collection involve: first, the dates of the reports from 28th October to 4 November 2024, when the coverage of the media was precise about the case of Vini Jr. and the Ballon d'Or award. Secondly, in sports journalism, the selection of the reports was based on authority, reputation, and international leadership. The Guardian and BBC journals represent common and public perspectives within British media, while ESPN and The New York Times journals offer distinct coverage within American media.

The process of data collection was cautiously planned to ensure that the selection of the texts reflects credible and diverse instances of racial discourse in sports media. By using clear and crucial criteria, the study gathers a collection that is appropriate for conducting CDA while sustaining the focus and relevance important for a case study approach. The following table provides the details of the data:

Table 7*Details of Data Collection*

British and American Journals	Title	Date	Links
BBC	Report (1): 'Injustice' - Brazil reacts to Vinicius Jr snub.	2024, October 29	https://www.bbc.com/sport/football/articles/c0k8vmg0p57o
	Report (2): 'Him against the world' - how Vinicius Jr's fight goes beyond football	2024, November 4	https://www.bbc.com/sport/football/articles/cp9zn5439v0o
The Guardian	Real Madrid cancel plans to attend Ballon d'Or as club believe Vinicius will not win	2024, October 28	https://www.theguardian.com/football/2024/oct/28/real-madrid-cancel-plans-to-attend-ballon-dor-as-club-believe-vinicius-will-not-win
	Real Madrid Ballon d'Or boycott ushers in the age of the super-sulk	2024, October 29	https://www.theguardian.com/football/2024/oct/29/real-madrid-ballon-dor-vinicius-rodri
The New York Times	Vinicius Jr's Ballon d'Or chances harmed by success of Real Madrid teammates, awards chief suggests	2024, October 29	https://www.nytimes.com/athletic/5882174/2024/10/29/vinicius-ballon-dor-voting/?searchResultPosition=1&redirected=1
	Vinicius Junior, Ballon d'Or disappointment, and Real Madrid's furious reaction	2024, October 29	https://www.nytimes.com/athletic/5880874/2024/10/29/vinicius-junior-ballon-dor-real-madrid-anger/?searchResultPosition=8
ESPN	Ballon d'Or: Real Madrid, Brazil stars back Vinicius after snub	2024, October 30	https://www.espn.com/soccer/story/_/id/42067979/ballon-dor-real-madrid-brazil-stars-back-vinicius-snob
	Can Vinicius Jr. rise above Ballon d'Or snub? It's up to him	2024, October 31	https://www.espn.com/soccer/story/_/id/42192252/vinicius-jr-ballon-dor-snob-brazil-real-madrid-laliga-champions-league

3.2.1 Comprehensive Evolution of the Ballon d'Or

The Ballon d'Or was first awarded in 1956 by France Football (a weekly sports magazine and the organizer of the Ballon d'Or), and persists as one of the most important individual awards in global football. As stated by The Guardian (2010), the award was “organised by French Football magazine”, and was the creation of the editor Jacques Ferran and the journalist Gabriel Hanot. The award, according to FIFA (2016), was restricted to European players, and over the decades, its scope expanded. In 1995, the qualification was expanded to non-European players at European clubs, and through 2007, the award was opened to all players (Ferreira, 2018).

France Football (FF) collaborated with FIFA from 2010 to 2015 by merging the Ballon d'Or with the FIFA World Player Award. The two organizations (FF, FIFA) declared, “finally took the plunge and merged their awards in 2010, to create the FIFA Ballon d'Or” (Edwards, 2016). However, according to the news reports (Goal.com), in September 2016, that arrangement was dissolved when FIFA chose not to renew the relationship. As Edwards (2016) provided, “the deal finally ended in September 2016, when FIFA pulled the plug on their association”. FIFA and FF reportedly had a “significant disagreement” on sponsorship arrangements and rules, which led FIFA to withdraw (Krishnan, 2023). After that, FF returned the Ballon d'Or to its original format (voting via journalists only), while FIFA reinstated its own awards (The Best FIFA Men's Player from 2016 onward) (Edwards, 2016).

According to the Union of European Football Associations (UEFA) (2023), in late 2023, FF began a new collaboration, this time with UEFA. In an official report announcement dated 3 November 2023, UEFA declared that “UEFA and Group Amaury (French media and publishing company) have today announced a partnership to co-organise the renowned Ballon d'Or from 2024” (UEFA, 2023). The goal of this collaboration is to “enhance the stature and global reach of the awards” through the stewardship of FF with UEFA's organizational and marketing resources.

Under the agreement, Groupe Amaury remains the owner of the Ballon d'Or brand, and its well-known voting system will stay “unchanged and independent” (UEFA, 2023).

In recent decades, as asserted by *The Guardian* journal (2024), critics have noted that the Ronaldo-Messi duopoly (from 2008 to 2023 saw those two win 13 of 15 awards) made the award something of a foregone conclusion (Reid, 2024). The award in 2024 prompted noise in many quarters. According to the BBC journal (2024), in Brazil, the result was mainly denounced as a “missed opportunity” or “unjust”. The BBC reported that Brazilian commentators called the decision of Rodri over Vini “unjust” and even “the most controversial decision in the award’s history”. In Brazil, many questioned whether racial prejudice affected the voting, observing the prominent stance of Vini Jr. against racism (Diniz, 2024). Outside Brazil, according to the *Sports Illustrated* journal (2025), Cristiano Ronaldo described the win of Rodri as “unfair”, insisting Vini “deserved to win the 2024 Ballon d’Or” (Langell, 2025). Real Madrid club influentially boycotted the 2024 ceremony in protest, calling the decision “unfair”, “a disgrace”, and “a historic robbery” (Hofman & Faez, 2024).

The career of the Real Madrid player Vini Jr. has become mainly tied to recent Ballon d’Or discourse. As declared by TNT Sports journal (2024), Vini “has been the favourite to win the 2024 Ballon d’Or for months” (Bray, 2024). Correspondingly, ESPN journal (2024) noted that the 24-year-old was “a leading contender to win the 2024 men’s prize” after his campaign (Hofman & Faez, 2024). In Brazil, the incident sparked more talks about race and recognition; one sports editor said that not giving the Ballon d’Or to Vini was a comprehensive “injustice” in the history award (Diniz, 2024).

The current study investigates racism in British and American journals, as well as the case study in the 2024 Ballon d’Or award.

3.3 Steps of Data Analysis

The study adopts the CDA approach and is supported by complementary frameworks, through which it aims to uncover how racism is presented in sport discourse linguistically and discursively, as far as media coverage of the 2024 Ballon d'Or award and the exclusion of Vini Jr. are concerned. To attain this, the following steps were followed:

- 1- **Data Sources Identification:** Eight reports are chosen from four recognized journals, including two British (BBC, The Guardian) and two American (ESPN, The New York Times). Two reports were chosen from each journal, and two extracts from each report were selected, resulting in a total of sixteen extracts for analysis.
- 2- **Analytical Framework Demonstration:** The analysis of the data included an integrated model based on Fairclough's three-dimensional framework (1989, 2001), reinforced by Halliday and Matthiessen's (2014), Fairhurst and Sarr's FT (1996), and Delgado and Stefancic's CRT (2001).
- 3- **Clause-based Analysis:** Each selected extract will be divided into individual clauses, affording for linguistic and discursive analysis. Such clause analysis affirms precise identification of process types, modality, mood, appraisal system, and thematic structure.
- 4- **Description Stage Analysis:** Each extract is analyzed by its vocabulary, thematic structure, mood, modality, transitivity, and cohesion. Halliday's SFL is employed to examine the ideational, interpersonal, and textual metafunctions of language.
- 5- **Interpretation Stage Analysis:** This stage is concerned with the way framing devices such as metaphors, stories, traditions, jargon, slogans, catchphrases, artifacts, contrasts, and spins were used to influence public perception and specific ideologies. FT is employed to show the rhetorical strategies included in the discourse.

- 6- **Explanation Stage Analysis:** By applying CRT, this stage uncovers how racial ideologies and institutional bias were included in or deleted from the discourse. Five central principles by Delgado and Stefancic (2001): Ordinary, Interest Convergence, Social Construction of Race, Unique Voice of Color, and Counter Storytelling are applied to uncover the ideological critique.
- 7- **Findings Synthesis:** After the analysis of all extracts' thematic consistencies, patterns will be examined through the analytical framework to evaluate the way British and American sports media coverage linguistically and discursively creates or resists racism in the context of the football award.
- 8- **Results of Research Questions and Aims:** The results of the analysis are interpreted based on research questions and aims to identify the way media discourse on the Ballon d'Or award contributes to the challenge or reproduction of racial injustice in global media coverage.

3.4 Analytical Framework

CDA includes various approaches, each of which is useful and gives a different explanation and deals with discourse from different perspectives, supported by other linguistic frameworks and theories. Therefore, Fairclough's Three-Dimensional Framework (1989, 2001), Halliday and Matthiessen's SFL (2014), Fairhurst and Sarr's FT (1996), and Delgado and Stefancic's CRT (1996) are preferable for the current study. Each framework contributes to a particular analytical dimension, constructing a significant model for analyzing the language of sports journalism, specifically in contexts including institutional injustice and racial representation. In addition to enhancing the analytical depth to each level, the current study integrates three additional

frameworks, namely, Halliday and Matthiessen's SFL (2014), Fairhurst and Sarr's FT (1996), and Delgado and Stefancic's CRT (1996). This combined framework allows a critical interpretation of the way language, racism, and ideology interrelate to the coverage of the 2024 Ballon d'Or award and the exclusion of Vini Jr.

The analysis is carried out through three incorporated stages, following Fairclough's theoretical framework. The steps of analysis are as follows:

1- Description Stage and SFL: This stage focuses on linguistic and structural features of the texts, involving vocabulary, cohesion, intertextuality, thematic structure, transitivity, and modality. This stage involves Halliday's SFL, which focuses on three central metafunctions to analyze the language:

A- Ideational metafunction: deals with how events, experiences, and processes are represented. It explores transitivity structures, encompassing process type (material, verbal, mental, relational, behavioral, existential), participants (actor, goal), and circumstances.

B- Interpersonal metafunction: deals with how language creates relationships between the writer/speaker and the audience. Involves analysis of mood type (declarative, interrogative, imperative), modality (modal verbs, nouns, and adverbs), and evaluations (attitude, engagement, graduation).

C- Textual metafunction: investigates how information is coherent and structured. This involves theme/rheme structures, cohesive devices, and text organization.

2- Interpretation Stage and FT: This stage uncovers the way texts are framed, produced, and interpreted in language. FT is employed to identify specific techniques by Fairhurst and Sarr (1996) for the analysis, such as: metaphor (comparing or systematizes a new idea),

contrast (describe a topic via what it includes and excludes), stories (framing a topic), tradition (ritual and define an organization), jargon, slogans, and catchphrases, (present a topic notably and memorably), artifacts (clarifying commercial values), and spin (describing a concept positively or negatively). Which aids in showing the way media discourses influence the audience perception and is associated with a larger ideological frame.

3- Explanation Stage and CRT: The final stage positions the discourse within its larger ideological, social, and historical context. It associates CRT to state the way racism, power, and exclusion are included or excluded within the discourse. Precisely, the study focuses on five CRT principles described by Delgado and Stefancic (2001): ordinary (racism is a normalized experience, not an exception), interest convergence/material discrimination (racial justice is recognized when it align with the dominant or interests), social construction of race (how race constructed via discourse), unique voice of color (individuals have special recognized experiential knowledge), and legal storytelling (personal narratives use to challenge dominant groups and uncover inequality).

By integrating this analytical framework, which assigns a comprehensive approach to CDA. The three-dimensional approach of Fairclough organizes the process, while SFL states the linguistic metafunctions for constructing meanings. FT illustrates the way meaning is framed and interpreted, and CRT reveals the racialized power dynamics included in the discourse. Along with these theories help to maintain a critical reading of media texts, allowing for emphasizing the way sports journalism constructs, reflects, and shapes ideologies of race, racism, and its ideological implications in the context of the Ballon d'Or award 2024.

Figure 6

The Eclectic Model

3.5 Validity and Reliability

Validity and reliability, as stated by Patton (2001), are two factors through which any qualitative researcher must be informed about analyzing results and judging the quality of the work. Golafshani (2003) stated that “to ensure reliability in qualitative research, examination of trustworthiness is important” (p.106). Stiles illustrates that reliability deals with the trustworthiness of data or observation (1993). Nunan explained that reliability “can be achieved through certain concepts such as consistency, dependability, and replicability. As far as validity is concerned, Johnson (1997) sets three types of validity, including: descriptive validity, which refers to the accuracy of the data. Interpretive validity encompasses the degree to which the viewpoints, experiences, and thoughts of the participants are precisely recognized and reported by the researcher. Theoretical validity refers to the degree to which the theory suits the analyzed data to be credible. According to Ajmal (2009), validity is “a further name for truth” (p.73).

As far as this study is concerned, validity and reliability are stated through dependability, credibility, and transferability. Validity confirmed by addressing the analysis established theoretical approaches, Fairclough’s CDA, Halliday’s SFL, FT, and CRT. These approaches reinforce the trustworthiness of the findings and maintain an exact interpretation of race, power, and ideologies in media texts. Reliability is achieved via clear documentation of data collection, a reliable step-by-step approach, an analytical method, using explicit theoretical devices, and auditability by detailed linguistic evidence, ensuring that the study is theoretically and methodologically reliable.

3.6 Ethical Considerations

Ethical and legal considerations in the current study were observed to ensure academic responsibility, integrity, and transparency through the research process. The data were collected from publicly accessible journalists' sources, precise reports from BBC, The Guardian, ESPN, and The New York Times. Thus, full acknowledgment was given to all sources, and suitable academic citation protocols were followed to respect intellectual property and avoid plagiarism. Furthermore, the analysis was conducted with societal awareness and sensitivity to the social implications of discourse, specifically when analyzing narratives about racial identity and marginalization. These precautions are crucial to maintain both the ethical standards of qualitative research and the legal expectations about using published media content.

Chapter Four

Data Analysis and Discussion

4.0 Introduction

This chapter presents the analysis of the selected data based on the adopted framework. The three stages of Fairclough’s dimensional approach are central, and apply to each stage a specific model of analysis, namely, the description stage with SFL’s metafunctions, the interpretation stage with FT’s techniques, and the explanation stage with CRT’s principles.

4.1 Analysis of British Journals

4.1.1 BBC News Sports Reports, Report (1): “‘Injustice’ – Brazil reacts to Vinicius Jr snub, 29 October, 2024”

4.1.1.1 Analysis of Extract (1)

News commentators described the decision as an unjust and retaliatory move, with some concluding that it was the most controversial decision in the award's history. Many claimed the Real Madrid player was denied the award because of his stance on the racism he faces in Spain. We know that Vinicius is a target of racism in Spanish football and other parts of Europe, and he actively fights against racism, said Guga Chacra, a commentator from the leading Brazilian TV news network Globo News. This leads us to question whether the result that gave Rodri the win was influenced by prejudice and racism against Vinicius.

This extract presents a media response to the Ballon d’Or decision, asserting that Vini was unjustly denied the award because of his assertive stance against racism.

At the description stage, the clause “*News commentators described the decision as an unjust and retaliatory move*” is declarative and constructed by the verbal process “*described*” with “*News commentators*” serving as the sayer, and “*the decision*” as the verbiage/phenomenon, then

the relational aspect is depicted in the evaluative nature of the clause, connecting the decision to negative attributes “*unjust, retaliatory*”. In the system of appraisal, this clause expresses attitude via negative judgment; the use of engagement is heteroglossically (a third-party voice), and includes graduation through the intensifying language of condemnation. The theme of the clause is topical: “*News commentators described the decision as an unjust and retaliatory move*”, and the rheme carries the evaluative action, constructing a content theme pattern that reflects the type of decision made.

In the next clause, “*with some concluding that it was the most controversial decision in the award’s history,*” which is declarative; the central process is mental “*concluding*”, with “*some*” as the senser and “*it was the most controversial decision in the award’s history*” as the phenomenon. The relational process presented through using the verb to be “*was*” connects the pronoun “*it*” to the superlative phrase “*most controversial decision,*” shaping the judgment as a relational identification. The phrase “*most controversial*” states high epistemic modality, describing the issue concerning the Ballon d’Or event. As far as the appraisal system is concerned, attitude is expressed by means of negative judgment, engagement persists heteroglossic, and graduation is described by the superlative “*most*”, maximizing the evaluation force. The theme “*with some concluding that it was the most controversial decision in the award’s history*” states a new evaluating entity, the rheme explains the judgment, constructing a zigzag thematic pattern.

The clause “*Many claimed the Real Madrid player was denied the award because of his stance on the racism he faces in Spain*” is declarative and constructed through three processes including the verbal process presented through the verb “*claimed*”, and the material process in the passive voice “*was denied*”, and the goal for both is “*the Real Madrid player*”. A mental process is faintly included through “*stance*”, with the prepositional phrase “*on racism*” describing the player in the context of the action taking place. The material process is presented again depicting

the identity of the player by means of connotation through the relative clause “*he faces in Spain*” in which “*he*” stands for Vinicius, “*faces*” is the material process, and the circumstance “*in Spain*” refers directly to the place where Vini conflict has begun. This clause is preceded by the causal connector “*because of,*” indicating modality of reason, connecting the player and the award to racism through medium-to-high epistemic certainty. The system of appraisal involves an attitude that is expressed through negative judgment for systemic injustice, engagement is dialogic expansion by attributing the claim, and the graduation is categorical assertion. The theme “*Many claimed the Real Madrid player was denied the award because of his stance on the racism he faces in Spain*” serves interpersonally, sustaining the collective voice critique, and the rheme includes the essential ideational message, persisting in the constant theme pattern presented through “*was denied the award because of his stance on the racism he faces in Spain*”.

The fourth clause, “*We know that Vinicius is a target of racism in Spanish football and other parts of Europe, and he actively fights against racism,*” is declarative and starts with a mental process “*know*” where “*we*” is the senser, preceded by a relational process “*is*” in “*is a target*”, and the material process “*fights*” in the second conjunct. The epistemic modality is high because of “*we know*”, indicating certainty. The appraisal system is an attitude that involves negative affect “*target of racism,*” and positive judgment “*actively fights.*” While engagement is monoglossic, graduation is emphasized in “*actively,*” which increases the stance. The theme is “*We know that Vinicius is a target of racism in Spanish football and other parts of Europe, and he actively fights against racism,*” and the rheme includes the racial and activist identity of Vinicius. The pattern of the theme is both constant and interpersonal.

The final clause, “*This leads us to question whether the result that gave Rodri the win was influenced by prejudice and racism against Vinicius,*” is declarative and the central process is material presented in the verb “*leads*”, preceded by an included verbal process “*to question*” and

further embedded relational process “*was influenced*” it indicates speculative modality via “*question whether*” softening the force of accusation. The expressed attitude is negative “*prejudice, racism*”, engagement reopens the dialogue space through gaining the reader's contemplation, while graduation is in “*leads us*”, stating inevitability. The theme “*This leads us to question whether the result that gave Rodri the win was influenced by prejudice and racism against Vinicius*” is anaphorically refers to a prior context, and the rheme states the ethical tension of bias. The pattern of theme/rheme is both zigzag and textual, connecting prior discourse to new evaluative conclusions.

In the interpretation level, the textual and grammatical aspects of FT will be framed by using certain techniques such as metaphor, contrast, spin, stories, artifacts, and slogans/catchphrases. These are central to uncovering the way text discursively states the actors, constructs ideological meaning, and engages the reader emotionally. In the first clause, “*News commentators described the decision as an unjust and retaliatory move,*” the clause includes slogans and spin to frame the decision negatively. Using “*unjust, retaliatory,*” it presents the decision within a morally discredited frame, asserting a punitive motivation. The sayer “*News commentators*” frames as an artifact, they depict external, professional legitimacy, which improves the influence of their judgment.

The second clause, “*With some concluding that it was the most controversial decision in the award's history,*” by using a superlative language, “*most controversial,*” presents graduation and frames a catchphrase. The phrase, again, operates as a slogan within a broader discourse, enhancing the emotional and historical framing of the issue. The contrast here stated between the decision concerning the Ballon d’Or and its outcomes, affirming that other decisions were less controversial, more justified, or accepted without conflict. The adjectival phrase “*most controversial*” signals a break in the award tradition of objectivity and legitimacy. Along with the

contrast between what the decision should state (excellence, merit) and what is framed as “*controversial, retaliatory*” is basic to the way the audience is encouraged to understand the event as biased or flawed. The clause also framed the artifact of the award, transforming it from a neutral tradition into a subject of critique.

The third clause, “*Many claimed the Real Madrid player was denied the award because of his stance on the racism he faces in Spain,*” represents ideological and narrative-driven framing. Emphasizing the use of myth framing or storytelling, through which the player is framed as a principled figure punished for moral resistance. The word “*denied*” adds to the spin, enhancing the idea of unjust exclusion. The mention of “*his stance on racism*” and the causal connector “*because of*” strengthens the narrative framing. The use of “*Many*” sustains the collective judgment repetition, expanding the frame of concern and enhancing consensus.

In the fourth clause, “*We know that Vinicius is a target of racism in Spanish football and other parts of Europe, and he actively fights against racism,*” using a metaphor, “*a target of racism*” is comprehensive and frames Vini as a defenseless, yet active figure within a morally charged conflict. The coordinate clause “*he actively fights against racism*” presents a contrast between him and the silent or complicit institution. The phrase “*We know*” is monoglossic, serving as a rhetorical closure of doubt. The whole clause deepens the emotional stance of the narrative and aids the earlier strategies of framing by shifting from institutional critique to personal valor.

The final clause, “*This leads us to question whether the result that gave Rodri the win was influenced by prejudice and racism against Vinicius,*” states a spin in its core form. The use of the construction “*leads us to question*” implies a direct accusation of the awarding institution, yet it frames speculative doubt and potential institutional racism. It is also a frame of contrast, where the anti-racism of Vini is compared to the symbolic victory of Rodri. The use of the lexical “*prejudice, racism*” strengthens the emotional and ideological cohesion of the narrative, also using “*This*” as

a textual theme, which is another type of framing in accordance with the prior framing techniques. The clause maintains the tension between exclusion and recognition, politics and performance.

Throughout the five clauses, the repetition of particular linguistic aspects maintains a cohesive and ideologically loaded narrative. The use of the noun “*decision*” repeated in the first and second clauses represents the discourse in the institutional act under scrutiny. The continuing invocation of “*racism*” in three clauses third, fourth, and fifth, transforms it from a passing concern to the main ethical theme of the text, and therefore frames the discourse within the broader struggle for racial justice. Correspondingly, mentioning “*Vinicius*” explicitly (as Vinicius) and implicitly as “*the Real Madrid player*” represents him as the symbolic protagonist, as an active figure in resistance and injustice. The systemic use of “*News commentators, some, many, and we*” emphasizes the sense of public consensus and moral legitimacy. Moreover, terms such as “*award, result, win*” emphasize the institutional and symbolic value of the Ballon d’Or. Thus, the repetition stresses the main message that the decision of the award is not only controversial but also politically and racially charged, transforming sports outcomes into a narrative of injustice.

As far as the explanation stage is concerned, the clauses collectively construct a discourse that revolves around the racialized experience of Vini Jr. within a European football institution, uncovering the way language, evaluation, and framing offer deeper ideological tension. The repeated references to “*News commentators, some, many, and we*” and the lexical words “*unjust, retaliatory, most controversial, prejudice, and racism*” play an important role in framing the decision made against him as discriminatory. By the linguistic construction of the passive “*was denied*,” the text excludes the responsible actor. The racialized experience of Vini is emphasized via the mental and relational processes representing him as “*a target of racism*” and someone who “*actively fights against racism*,” stating his ideological positioning not just as a player but as a resister of injustice. The principle of interest convergence is constructed by how the exclusion of

Vini from the Ballon d'Or stems not from performance but from the threat of his anti-racism stance. Therefore, such clauses uncover how Vini was denied the award and exposed to layers of symbolic exclusion that illustrate racial power dynamics within elite football.

4.1.1.2 Analysis of Extract (2)

The fact that Vini Jr wasn't awarded the title of best player in the world at the Ballon d'Or is yet another way to try to penalise the Brazilian for his outspoken stance on racial issues, both on and off the field," wrote Douglas Ceconello, a journalist for Globo Esporte, a sports website in Brazil. Following the Ballon d'Or results, Vinicius posted a message on X which said: "I will do it 10 times if I have to. They are not ready." His post received over 100,000 comments, with many Brazilians showing their support. Brazil's minister of racial equality, Anielle Franco, reacted to the message and said: "You are amazing, Vini! Racism will never stop us. Let's keep making history.

During the description stage, the clause *"The fact that Vini Jr wasn't awarded the title of best player in the world at the Ballon d'Or is yet another way to try to penalise the Brazilian for his outspoken stance on racial issues, both on and off the field"* is declarative. As it involves a relational process "is" connecting *"he fact that Vini Jr wasn't awarded the title of best player in the world at the Ballon d'Or is yet"* to the understanding of it as *"another way to try to penalise"*. Within the sentence, there is a material process *"wasn't awarded"* that reveal an action happening to Vini. He is the goal in the process, through which he is affected by the action. This clause involves a mental intent *"to try to penalise"* that affirms a purpose behind the action. The system of appraisal uncovers strong negative attitude with phrases like *"penalise"* and *"outspoken stance on racial issues"* which holds judgment and emotion. The theme is *"The fact that Vini Jr wasn't awarded the title of best player in the world at the Ballon d'Or;"* and the phrase includes *"is yet another way to try to penalise the Brazilian for his outspoken stance on racial issues, both on and off the field"* is the rheme. The full sentence reveals the way the writer frames the denial of the award as unfair punishment for Vini's ant-racist activism.

The second clause, *“Following the Ballon d’Or results, Vinicius posted a message on X which said: I will do it 10 times if I have to. They are not ready”* is declarative. The material process is *“posted”* when Vini is the actor and *“a message”* is the goal. Within the message, the phrase *“I will do it 10 times if I have to”* uncovers modality via necessity and willingness, while *“they are not ready”* involves a mental process where Vini evaluates the readiness of others. The theme is *“Following the Ballon d’Or results, Vinicius posted a message on X which said”* and the rheme is *“I will do it 10 times if I have to. They are not ready”*. This sentence uncovers Vini's strong reaction to the injustice he feels.

The clause *“His post received over 100,000 comments, with many Brazilians showing their support”* is declarative. Including a material process is *“received”* and *“his post”* as the actor, and *“over 100,000 comments”* as the goal. The sentence *“many Brazilians showing their support”* serves as a material process, where *“many Brazilians”* are the actors, where *“showing”* is material, and *“their support”* is the goal. The attitude is positive, as it reveals solidarity with Vini. The theme is *“His post received over 100,000 comments”* and the rheme *“with many Brazilians showing their support,”* which means that Vini is not struggling alone.

The final clause, *“Brazil’s minister of racial equality, Aniello Franco, reacted to the message and said: ‘You are amazing, Vini! Racism will never stop us. Let’s keep making history’”* is declarative. It involves two verbal processes: *“reacted”* and *“said”*. The sayer is *“Aniello Franco”*. Within the quote, there are distinct process types: *“You are amazing”* is a relational process connecting *“you”* to *“amazing”*, *“Racism will never stop us”* involves a material process *“stop”* with *“racism”* as the actor and *“us”* as the goal. Another statement *“Let’s keep making history,”* is a mental/material motivational process. *“will never”* is considered a strong modality revealing certainty. The attitude is motivational and supportive. The theme is *“Brazil’s minister of racial equality, Aniello Franco, reacted to the message and said,”* and the rheme is *‘You are*

amazing, Vini! Racism will never stop us. Let's keep making history". This complete sentence offers institutional support to the cause of Vini and adds strength to his position.

At the interpretation stage, the following clauses will be framed by using FT. The clause "*The fact that Vini Jr wasn't awarded the title of best player in the world at the Ballon d'Or is yet another way to try to penalise the Brazilian for his outspoken stance on racial issues, both on and off the field*" will be framed by using spin. It presents the outcome of the award as a repeated act of punishment. The phrase "*yet another way to try to penalise*" represents intentional exclusion, depict the behavior of the decision as retaliatory. Also, the clause serves as a frame of storytelling, it forms a narrative through which Vini is a target because of his activism and values. The use of "*penalise*" is metaphorical, suggesting the image of his discipline. Framing Vini as "*the Brazilian*" states an international contrast, separating him from the norms of Europe.

The second clause, "*Following the Ballon d'Or results, Vinicius posted a message on X which said: I will do it 10 times if I have to. They are not ready,*" uses framing techniques like slogans and catchphrases. The words of Vini, "*I will do it 10 times if I have to,*" and "*They are not ready,*" function as personal slogans of resistance. The use of conditional tone constructs a resistance and a confirmation of keeping his own goals and attitudes. He uses "*they*" to present a contrast frame, making an opposition between himself (as a symbol of moral clarity and resiliency) and the social force (the unnamed institution) that rejects him.

The clause "*His post received over 100,000 comments, with many Brazilians showing their support*" integrates tradition and ritual framing. The size of the comments and the national support assert a collective social ritual of solidarity, where people interact to state a shared moral stance. The phrase "*many Brazilians showing their support*" frames the resistance of Vini not as alone but as broadly validated, enhancing the moral legitimacy of his message. It also functions as an artifact of emotional resonance, revealing that his words raised real-world engagement.

The final clause, “*Brazil’s minister of racial equality, Aniello Franco, reacted to the message and said: ‘You are amazing, Vini! Racism will never stop us. Let’s keep making history’*” includes multiple frames. The position of “*Aniello Franco*” is that of a government official who presents institutional authority and tradition, framing the response as politically supported. Her phrase “*Racism will never stop us. Let’s keep making history*” operates as slogans and catchphrases that reinforce national pride and collective resistance.

Through these five clauses, textual aspects are repeated to frame consistency. The name “*Vinicius*” is repeated in every clause, concerning resistance, moral strength, and exclusion, framing him as the main figure and the ideological focus of the discourse. The use of verbal processes “*wrote, said, posted*” implies the discourse as dialogue, encompassing multiple social voices. Repetitions of institution references “*Ballon d’Or, award, minister*” emphasize systemic involvement. Such repetitions make emphasis, coherence, and morality, arguing that Vini’s case is a part of a broader social and institutional critique instead of a personal case.

Specifically speaking, through the explanation stage, the text presents Vini as someone who is unjustly treated due to his strong position against racism. The passive phrase “*wasn’t awarded*” hides the people responsible and makes it seem like the system, not an individual, caused the damage. This is associated with the CRT of institutional racism, where racism serves through structures instead of overt actions. The phrase “*outspoken stance on racial issues*” uncovers that Vini is not silent; he utilizes his platform to speak out, which depicts the unique voice of color. Even though his message needs support from others, like Minister and journalists, stating that his voice alone might not be enough to make a change. His repeated stance on racism, specifically in Europe, and the lack of institutional recognition in the form of the Ballon d’Or, reveal how race can be socially created and utilized to exclude people from praise or power. The support of the minister can be associated with interest convergence, where the state supports anti-racist speech

when it aids its own image. Therefore, Vini is not seen as a football player, but rather as a figure who fights against discrimination.

4.1.1.3 Report (2): Extract (1) “Him against the world – how Vinicius Jr’s fight goes beyond football 4 November, 2024”

Since he became a key player in Real's team, La Liga has referred 21 racist incidents involving the superstar to local prosecutors, as a result of regular abuse from the stands, monkey chants and an effigy hung from a bridge being directed his way. In June, three Valencia fans were sentenced to eight months in prison for hate crimes against Vinicius, in the first conviction for racism-related cases in Spanish football stadiums. "I'm not a victim of racism. I'm the tormentor of racists," the 24-year-old posted on social media afterwards. "May other racists be afraid, ashamed and hide in the shadows. Otherwise, I'll be here to get you."

Regarding the description stage, the clause “*Since he became a key player in Real’s team*” is in a declarative mood. The process of the clause “*became*” is relational, revealing a change in the player’s role or identity. The carrier is “*he*”, and the attribute is “*a key player in Real’s team*”. It involves a time theme also, “*since*” which establishes the background for what is coming. The theme is “*Since he became a key player in Real’s team,*” and the rheme is leading to the next clause, which is implicit. Such a clause links Vini’s rise in status to the events that proceed, presenting a cause-and-effect relationship.

The second clause, “*La Lega has referred 21 racist incidents involving the superstar to local prosecutors,*” is declarative. It involves a material process “*has referred*”, and “*La Lega*” is the actor, the action is “*has referred*”, and “*21 racist incidents*” is the goal. The beneficiary is “*local prosecutors*”. The phrase “*involving the superstar*” is circumstantial and uncovers that Vini is affected. The modality is strong and factual. The theme is “*La Lega has referred 21 racist incidents involving the superstar to local prosecutors,*” and the rheme involves complete information about the institutional reaction to the issue. Such a clause encompasses the frequency and seriousness of racism against Vini.

The clause “*As a result of regular abuse from the stands, monkey chants and an effigy hung from a bridge being directed his way*” is dependent and serves as a circumstance of cause. It contains a material process “*being directed*” where “*abuse, chants, and effigy*” are the phenomena. The goal of the clause is “*his way*”. Such a clause employs a passive construction, which conceals the actor and concentrates on Vini as the one influenced. The theme is “*As a result of regular abuse from the stands, monkey chants and an effigy hung from a bridge being directed his way*” and the rheme is embedded in the main clause it supports. Symbolizing racism and the violence he faces.

The fourth clause, “*In June, three Valencia fans were sentenced to eight months in prison for hate crimes against Vinicius,*” is declarative with a material process “*were sentenced*”. The goal is “*three Valencia fans*”. The phrase “*for hate crimes against Vinicius*” is a circumstance of cause, revealing the reason for the punishment. The modality is strong and factual. The theme is “*In June, three Valencia fans were sentenced to eight months in prison for hate crimes against Vinicius,*” and the rheme maintains the fact. Such a clause highlights that legal consequences have eventually occurred in connection with racism that Vini endures.

In the next clause, “*I’m not a victim of racism*” holds a declarative mood with relational process “*am*”. The carrier is “*I*” (Vini), and the attribute is “*not a victim of racism*”. The theme is “*I’m not a victim of racism,*” and the rheme shifts the expected label of victim. It highlights a discursive shift through which Vini defines his own role. The other clause, “*I’m the tormentor of racists,*” is declarative with a relational process “*am*”. The carrier is “*I*”, and the attribute is “*the tormentor of racists*”. The modality is high and reveals certainty. The theme is “*I’m the tormentor of racists,*” and the rheme asserts the strength and the resistance of Vini. The clause is an influential reversal of victimhood and creates an active identity.

The clause “*May other racists be afraid, ashamed and hide in the shadows*” is imperative and holds the modal verb “*May*”. The material processes are “*be afraid, ashamed, hide*”. The actor

is “*other racists*,” and the goal is “*in the shadows*.” The theme is “*May other racists be afraid, ashamed and hide in the shadows*,” and the rheme states Vini’s request for justice via fear and shame. The final clause “*Otherwise, I’ll be here to get you*” is declarative with a conditional mood “*Otherwise*”. The actor is “*I*” and the material process “*will be here to get you*”. The goal is “*you*” (racists); such a clause utilizes resistance and threat as a rhetorical strategy. The theme is “*Otherwise, I’ll be here to get you*,” and the rheme enhances the active role of Vini in challenging racism directly.

At the interpretation stage, aligning with FT, in the first clause, “*Since he became a key player in Real’s team*,” the rise of Vini to prominence acts as a trigger frame, affirming that his visibility led to the way racist attacks increased. The second clause, “*La Lega has referred 21 racist incidents involving the superstar to local prosecutors*,” employs artifact framing to uncover institutional response. Though it highlights the way these attacks frequently happened, arguing that racism is not incidental but structural. The third clause, “*As a result of regular abuse from the stands, monkey chants and an effigy hung from a bridge being directed his way*,” frames racism via symbolic imagery, specifically, in “*monkey chants, effigy*,” which are loaded with emotional and violent symbols. These loaded expressions function as a metaphoric framing, uncovering not only dislike but enduring dehumanization. The next clause, “*In June, three Valencia fans were sentenced to eight months in prison for hate crimes against Vinicius*,” employs a ritual framing: it states the decision of the court as a rare moment of accountability. The fifth and sixth clauses, “*I’m not a victim of racism*”, “*I’m the tormentor of racists*”, use contrast and slogan framing. He refuses to be considered a victim and rather calls himself “*the tormentor of racists*”. This shows the power dynamics, turning shame and fear back on the oppressor. Clause seven, “*May other racists be afraid, ashamed and hide in the shadows*,” utilizes imperative framing, presenting social and emotional consequences for racists. Finally, the clause “*Otherwise, I’ll be here to get you*”

reinforces the heroic contrast theme, which frames Vini as an active defender of justice instead of a passive target.

The word “*racism*” occurred multiple times, and always refers to Vini; it is the central issue of the discourse. The word “*racists*” is repeated in 6-7 clauses, changing the main concern from systemic injustice to personal confrontation. The name “*Vinicius*” and his self-reference “*I*” construct a consistent voice of resistance. Material processes like “*directed, were sentenced, get you, and hide*” are repeated and emphasize an action, either inflicted upon or taken by Vini, highlighting his role in responding to and suffering injustice.

As far as the explanation stage is concerned, the clauses expose the way Vini is always subjected to both symbolic and physical racism, not by repeated incidents but also via how individuals and institutions react to them. The extract uncovers that his racial role made him a visible target of abuse, and also a powerful voice of resistance. The passive construction “*being directed his way*” and the metaphor “*effigy*” emphasize the way dehumanization functions without clear agents, reflecting the view of CRT of racism as included in systems instead of individual acts. Vini’s statements, “*I’m not a victim of racism*”, “*I’m the tormentor of racists*,” show the principle of the unique voice of color, where those impacted speak back and redefine the narrative. This can also be a type of counter/storytelling as he reframes himself not as one silenced by racism, but as one who actively confronts it. The legal sentence against the fans aligns with the principle of interest convergence. Through which justice occurs when it is associated with wider institutional interests. Therefore, this discourse uncovers the ideology concerning Vini as moral clarity, pride, and resistance. His language questions the silence and delay of institutions and reveals how racism can be directly and powerfully resisted.

4.1.1.4 Extract (2)

Despite being reduced to tears in a press conference as he admitted the toll the situation has had on him, Vinicius has not backed down in his mission and has become the leading black voice in challenging racism in football.

In regard to the description stage, the first clause, “*Despite being reduced to tears in a press conference as he admitted the toll the situation has had on him,*” is in declarative mood. It serves as a circumstantial clause of concession, and includes a material process “*being reduced to tears*” in passive form. The goal is “*he*” (Vini). The phrase “*as he admitted the toll*” adds a verbal process “*admitted*”, along with “*he*” as the sayer, and “*the toll the situation has had on him*” as the verbiage. The embedded clause “*the situation has had on him*” involves a relational process “*has had*”, with “*the situation*” as the carrier and “*a toll*” as an attribute portraying emotional damage. The theme is “*Despite being reduced to tears in a press conference as he admitted the toll the situation has had on him,*” and the rheme is the consequence that follows in the next clause. Such a clause reveals how Vini suffers from constant racism and prepares the contrast of resilience in the next clause.

The next clause, “*Vinicius has not backed down in his mission,*” is declarative. The process is material “*has not backed down*”, and the actor is “*Vinicius*”. The circumstance is “*in his mission,*” revealing his constant goal. Through using negation “*not backed down*” and the perfect aspect “*has*” maintains ongoing action. The theme is “*Vinicius has not backed down in his mission,*” and the rheme presents the ideological contrast to the suffering in the previous clause. Such a clause uncovers Vini as resilient and persistent in opposing emotional damage. And the final clause, “*And has become the leading black voice in challenging racism in football,*” continues the prior one and is also declarative. The process is relational, “*has become*” with “*he*” as the

carrier and "*leading black voice in challenging racism in football*" as the attribute. This clause includes a strong ideational element connecting race, activism, and voice. The theme is "*And has become the leading black voice in challenging racism in football*", and the rheme emphasizes the social and ideological role of Vini. This clause forms Vini's identity not only as a player but rather as a public active figure, contrasting racial injustice.

As far as FT is concerned, the first clause, the phrase "*being reduced to tears,*" offers an emotional contrast frame that highlights the weakness of Vini. The word "*Despite*" emphasizes a contrast between subsequent strength and emotional pain. The tears and the conference of the press operate as an artifact, symbolizing a public expression of suffering by an athlete, specifically a Black male athlete. The verbal process, "*he admitted the toll the situation has had on him,*" serves as storytelling, showing a personal narrative that links the public with the suffering of Vini. This creates sympathy while emphasizing the seriousness of the racial attacks he faces. In the next clause, "*Vinicius has not backed down in his mission,*" there is a slogan, especially "*has not backed down,*" which frames Vini as strong. This phrase also functions as a catchphrase of resistance, sustaining expectations that someone is facing. The clause, "*And has become the leading black voice in challenging racism in football,*" elevates the prior clause, presenting a contrast to put Vini against a wider background of inaction or silence in football. It also utilizes heroic framing, depicting him as a moral leader. The phrase "*leading black voice*" is an influential discursive move that connects activism, race, and identity, turning Vini into a symbolic representative of a racial justice movement in the sport.

During the explanation stage, this extract explains the way Vini is portrayed as both a victim of systemic racism and a symbol of resistance against it. The refusal of Vini to "*black down*" and his alteration into the "*leading black voice*" maintains the principle of CRT's unique color of voice. Where those affected redefine their roles and resist dominant narratives. Vini's identity as a

“*Black voice*” challenges racism and enhances the principle of social construction of race. He is not considered a football player but also as a Black man whose role is influenced by racialized expectations. Rather than being diminished and silenced, he affirms both his power and voice, becoming a figure of racial resistance in global football culture.

4.1.2 Analysis of The Guardian

4.1.2.1 Report (1): Extract (1): “Real Madrid cancel plans to attend Ballon d’Or as club believe Vinicius will not win”

Bookmakers had 24-year-old Vinicius, the Champions League player of the year, as the heavy odds-on favourite to claim his first Ballon d’Or, which is presented to the best player in the world, ahead of Manchester City’s Spain midfielder Rodri and Real’s England international Jude Bellingham.

At the description level, the first clause “*Bookmakers had 24-year-old Vinicius, the Champions League player of the year, as the heavy odds-on favourite to claim his first Ballon d’Or*” is in declarative mood. It includes a relational process “*had*” that operates to claim status. The carrier is “*Bookmakers*”, while the goal is “*Vinicius*” or the identified participant. “*the heavy odds-on favourite to claim his first Ballon d’Or*” is the attribute. The phrase “*the Champions League player of the year*” functions as an embedded attribute that states justifications for the status. The theme is “*Bookmakers had 24-year-old Vinicius, the Champions League player of the year, as the heavy odds-on favourite to claim his first Ballon d’Or*” and the rheme presents the expectation concerning the award. Such a clause emphasizes statistical favoritism and recognition based on merit.

The next clause, “*which is presented to the best player in the world,*” is declarative and embedded, and serves as a defining relative clause that provides details about the Ballon d’Or and

its purpose. The material process “*is presented*”, where the goal is “*the best player in the world*”. The use of indirect construction removes agency from the sentence. The theme is “*which is presented to the best player in the world*”, and the rheme presents the award and its significance. Such a clause enhances the idea that the Ballon d’Or stands for merits.

The final clause “*ahead of Manchester City’s Spain midfielder Rodri and Real’s England international Jude Bellingham*” is a circumstantial clause of contrast or comparison that functions as an extension to clause one. The clause does not involve a process verb, but it supports the evaluative form in clause one. The theme is “*ahead of Manchester City’s Spain midfielder Rodri and Real’s England international Jude Bellingham*”, and the rheme expresses the competitive context.

In terms of the interpretation stage, the first clause “*Bookmakers had 24-year-old Vinicius, the Champions League player of the year, as the heavy odds-on favourite to claim his first Ballon d’Or*” uses artifact contrast framing. Presenting Vini as “*the Champions League player of the year*” and “*odds-on favourite*” emphasizes indicators of achievement and superiority; these artifact frames his nomination as justified. The odds of Bookmakers suggest statistical legitimacy, a numerical expression of professional confidence. The second clause, “*which is presented to the best player in the world*,” states the award as a symbol of the highest value. In addition, the third clause, “*ahead of Manchester City’s Spain midfielder Rodri and Real’s England international Jude Bellingham*,” employs a contrast framing. It put Vini in a clear superiority over his peers. Through naming competitors and still stating Vini a the frontrunner, the clause creates a hierarchy that further supports the argument that he was the most deserving. Which expresses an injustice frame if he does not win.

During the explanation stage, this extract presents Vini as the most qualified nominee for the Ballon d’Or due to the objective measures of success, comparative superiority, age,

performance, and statistical predictions. Within CRT, interest convergence may be emphasized, through which racialized individuals only receive recognition when it is associated with institutional interest. The lack of the actor in “*which is presented to the best player in the world*” shows the way institutions obscure responsibility in award decisions. The identity of Vini as a Black player is not stated directly in the extract, but is constructed contextually via contrast with two players, “*Rodri, and Bellingham,*” representing the social construction of race. Therefore, the extract expresses a critical ideological movement; it presents Vini as deserving based on excellence, turning the sports award into a site of ideological struggle.

4.1.2.2 Extract (2)

Vinicius helped Real to a Champions League-La Liga double last term along with 21-year-old Bellingham, who was named La Liga’s MVP after scoring a career best 19 goals in a sparkling debut campaign and helping England reach the Euro 2024 final.

At the description stage, the first clause, “*Vinicius helped Real to a Champions League-La Liga double last term,*” is declarative and provides a factual statement. The verb “*helped*” implies a material process showing an action. The actor is “*Vinicius*”, the goal is “*Real*”, and the circumstance is “*to a Champions League-La Liga double last term*” through which he helped Real achieve success. The theme is “*Vinicius helped Real to a Champions League-La Liga double last term*”, and the rheme states the main achievements of Vini. Such a clause maintains the successful and active role of Vini in Real Madrid's victories.

The second clause, “*along with 21-year-old Bellingham,*” is a circumstantial adjunct of accompaniment (not a complete independent clause), but it serves textually to modify clause one. This clause shows an additive relation to Vini’s action. The theme is “*along with 21-year-old Bellingham*”, and the rheme modifies the prior claim via sharing credit with another player. The

next clause, “*who was named La Liga’s MVP*,” is declarative. It involves a material process in passive construction, “*was named*”, revealing an action happening to Bellingham, and the goal is “*who*”. The theme is “*who was named La Liga’s MVP*”, and the rheme shows the individual recognition that Bellingham received for his successes.

The other clause, “*after scoring a career best 19 goals in a sparkling debut campaign*,” is a dependent circumstantial clause of time presented by “*after*”. It includes a material process “*scoring*”, the actor is “*he*” (Bellingham), and the goal is “*a career best 19 goals*”. The theme is “*after scoring a career best 19 goals in a sparkling debut campaign*”, and the rheme states a further justification for why Bellingham was awarded MVP status. This clause stresses Bellingham’s successful statistics. Finally, the clause “*and helping England reach the Euro 2024 final*” is another dependent clause connected to the earlier one and functions as declarative. The material process is “*helping*” with “*England*” as the goal and “*reach the Euro 2024 final*” as the outcome. The theme is “*and helping England reach the Euro 2024 final*”, and the rheme enhances Bellingham’s international achievements.

Regarding the interpretation stage, the first clause, “*Vinicius helped Real to a Champions League-La Liga double last term*,” frames Vini as a contributor to basic club success. This utilizes artifact framing, stressing achievements (winning titles) as evidence of merit. Although the addition of “*along with 21-year-old Bellingham*” softens the contributions of Vini by sharing the credit. This contrast frame, a delicate competition between Vini and Bellingham. The third clause “*who was named La Liga’s MVP*” shifts the concern to Bellingham’s recognition. The absence of the actor in the passive sentence removes responsibility for the decision and introduces the award as a neutral fact, even if the award shows a subjective judgment. The clause, “*after scoring a career best 19 goals in a sparkling debut campaign*”, and “*and helping England reach the Euro 2024 final*,” construct a storytelling and artifact frames, forming a heroic narrative about Bellingham.

Therefore, the entire extract frames Bellingham as a celebrated and more recognized figure, even though Vini's contributions are acknowledged.

As far as the explanation stage is concerned, the extract uncovers the way Vini's achievements are acknowledged, but not individually. While both players contributed to their club's certain victories, Bellingham's successes are institutionally rewarded (MVP award), whereas the contributions of Vini sustain part of a group narrative. Based on CRT, this explains the social construction of race, through which merit is not evaluated based on performance but is mediated through national racial identities. This passive construction, "*was named MVP*," illustrates how institutional decisions about recognition are neutralized and made for the same purpose, obscuring any bias behind them. Moreover, the focus on Bellingham's "*sparkling debut campaign*" and the international performance with England relates to interest convergence. Where narratives that strengthen European or success are more institutionally recognized. Therefore, the framing devalues Vini's successes relative to his European peer, exposing racial biases in the way excellence and merit are discursively created and rewarded in football media.

4.1.2.3 Report (2): Extract (1): "Real Madrid Ballon d'Or boycott ushers in the age of the super-sulk"

Now look, Vinícius is one of Football Daily's favourite players; we've been prattling on about him for years, long before you peasants. But the way Madrid are behaving, you'd think he was the lovechild of Diego Maradona and Roy Race who notched 812 goals last season.

In the description stage, the first clause, "*Now look*," is in the imperative mood; it contains a mental process, "*look*," focused on the audience. The senser is the reader/listener, and the phenomenon is implicit (to pay attention to what is coming). The theme is "*Now look*," and the

rheme implies (is to pay attention). It functions as an interpersonal plan to attract attention and signal that an evaluation is coming.

This clause, “*Vinicius is one of football Daily’s favourite players,*” is in declarative mood. It contains a relational process “*is*”, where “*Vinicius*” is the carrier and “*one of football Daily’s favourite players*” is the attribute. The theme is “*Vinicius is one of football Daily’s favourite players*”, and the rheme stresses the evaluation of Vini in a positive light. It creates a long-term positive perspective of Vini through media outlets. The other clause, “*we’ve been prattling on about him for years,*” is declarative. It includes a verbal process “*prattling on*”, where the sayer is “*we*” (Football Daily), “*about him*” (Vini) is the verbiage, and “*for years*” is a circumstance of time. The theme is “*we’ve been prattling on about him for years*”, and the rheme asserts the long-standing attention of the media to Vini. The next clause, “*long before you peasants,*” is a dependent temporal clause, functioning as a circumstantial adjunct. It encompasses an existential implication “*long before*”, affirming temporal superiority. The theme is “*long before you peasants*”, and the rheme assigns that Football Daily were fans compared to others (the audience).

The fifth clause, “*But the way Madrid are behaving,*” is a declarative dependent clause and affirms a comparison or evaluation. The process is behavioral “*are behaving*”, where “*Madrid*” is the behavior. The theme is “*But the way Madrid are behaving*”, and the rheme asserts the background or criticizes the actions of Real Madrid. Finally, the clause, “*you’d think he was the lovechild of Diego Maradona and Roy Race who notched 812 goals last season,*” is a hypothetical declarative clause presented by “*you’d think*”. The central mental process is “*think*”, where “*you*” (audience) is the sensor. The phenomenon is “*he was the lovechild of Diego Maradona and Roy Race who notched 812 goals last season*” within it, there is a relational process “*was*” and “*who notched 812 goals last season*” includes a material process “*notched*”, where “*who*” is the actor, and “*812 goals*” is the goal. The theme is “*you’d think he was the lovechild of Diego Maradona*

and Roy Race who notched 812 goals last season”, and the rheme exaggerates to criticize the way Madrid treats Vini as if he is beyond a legendary position.

During the interpretation stage, in the first clause, “*Now look,*” there's an attention framing, presenting to readers that a significant evaluative statement follows. The clause “*Vinicius is one of football Daily's favourite players*” frames Vini positively, stating him as one of the favorite players of Football Daily. Later, in clauses, “*we've been prattling on about him for years, long before you peasants,*” the framing is contrast and authority frames. Football Daily states itself above the general public, revealing Vini's talent. The use of “*peasants*” playfully reduces the credibility of other journalists or fans, enhancing Football Daily's position as insiders. Fifth clause “*But the way Madrid are behaving*” employs contrast framing. “*But,*” stating a shift, in which the speaker praises Vini, but criticizes how Madrid treat him. The final clause, “*you'd think he was the lovechild of Diego Maradona and Roy Race who notched 812 goals last season,*” exaggerates Madrid's treatment via metaphor. Arguing that Madrid acts as if Vini were a superhuman figure. Generally, the framing integrates affection for Vini with a critique of the way he is positioned by others, claiming that even those who love him see misjudgment in how institutions frame him.

Regarding the explanation stage, the extract uncovers the complex way Vini is positioned in media discourse. While Football Daily depicts him as respectable and lovely, they also expose how broader institutions may inflate his image to an unrealistic extent once he becomes an asset. This dynamic shows the principle of CRT of interest convergence; marginalized entities like Vini receive media and institutional support when they serve larger interests. Moreover, the funny exaggeration “*lovechild of Maradona and Roy Race*” asserts that the success of Vini is not seen as earned but should be exaggerated to be recognized, showing racialized expectations about how much brilliance a Black player reveals to be celebrated.

4.1.2.4 Extract (2)

Let's look at Vinicius' 2023-24 numbers. He was the joint-eighth top-scorer in La Liga, behind, among others, a Norwegian fella who couldn't get a game for Crystal Palace a few years ago. In the Champions League, the Brazilian scored six goals, one more than Stoke reject Joselu, who played 628 minutes fewer. At the Copa América he scored twice in the group stages, then got himself suspended and missed the quarter-final defeat to Uruguay.

As far as the description stage is concerned, the first clause, "*Let's look at Vinicius' 2023-24 numbers,*" is imperative, attracting the reader to be engaged. It contains a mental process "*look*", the senser is "*we*", and the phenomenon is "*Vinicius' 2023-24 numbers*". The appraisal system revolves around engagement. The theme is "*Let's look at Vinicius' 2023-24 numbers*", and the rheme creates a change to evaluate the performance of Vini.

The next clause, "*He was the joint-eighth top-scorer in La Liga,*" is in declarative mood, which states a fact. The process is relational "*was*", the carrier "*He*", and the attribute is "*the joint-eighth top-scorer in La Liga*". The clause expresses a neutral attitude in an appraisal system. The theme is the full clause "*He was the joint-eighth top-scorer in La Liga*", and the rheme reveals the position which asserts a mid-level success.

The third clause, "*behind, among others a Norwegian fella who couldn't get a game for Crystal Palace a few years ago,*" is a dependent, extending the prior one, and is in declarative mood. It includes the proposition "*behind*" along with a material process "*couldn't get a game*", the relational carrier, and the material actor represented through "*a Norwegian fella*". The modality depicted in the modal verb "*couldn't*", stating inability. The system of appraisal contains a negative attribute, the sentence "*a Norwegian fella who couldn't get a game*" expresses disparagement heading for the other player, claiming Vini was exceeded by someone with a weak record. The theme is "*behind, among others a Norwegian fella who couldn't get a game for Crystal Palace a few years ago*", and the rheme ironically minimizes the comparative standing of Vini.

The clause, “*In the Champions League, the Brazilian scored six goals,*” is declarative. It involves a material process “*scored*”, the actor is “*the Brazilian*”, while the goal is “*six goals*”. The appraisal system includes a positive attitude, including Vini’s achievements. Although by referring to Vini as “*the Brazilian,*” it states that there is an engagement. The theme is “*In the Champions League, the Brazilian scored six goals*”, while the rheme emphasizes a firm personal success.

The clause, “*one more than Stoke reject Joselu, who played 628 minutes fewer,*” illustrates the prior clause and is in declarative mood. The process is relational and inferred in “*one more than Stoke reject Joselu*” and a material process “*played*” for “*who played 628 minutes fewer.*” Joselu is both a carrier and an actor. The appraisal system is a negative attribute, calling Joselu a “*Stoke reject*” disparages him, which therefore minimizes Vini’s success by association. The theme is “*one more than Stoke reject Joselu, who played 628 minutes fewer*”, and the rheme devaluates the importance of Vini’s goal tally by recognizing the efficiency of another.

The other clause, “*At the Copa America he scored twice in the group stages*”, is declarative. It holds a material process “*scored*”, the actor is “*he*”, while the goal is “*twice*” (two goals). The appraisal system revolves around a neutral to positive attitude, as it records an achievement without exaggeration. The theme is the full clause “*At the Copa America he scored twice in the group stages*”, and the rheme focuses on reasonable accomplishments.

The final clause, “*then got himself suspended and missed the quarter-final defeat to Uruguay*”, is declarative. It uncovers two material processes: “*got himself suspended*” and “*missed*”. The actor implicitly “*he*”, and the goal is “*quarter-final defeat*”. The appraisal system shows a negative attitude; the suspension assigns a personal failure or lack of discipline. The theme is the full clause “*then got himself suspended and missed the quarter-final defeat to Uruguay*”, while the rheme puts Vini with absence and dissatisfaction at a pivotal moment.

In relation to the interpretation stage, the first clause, “*Let’s look at Vinicius’ 2023-24 numbers,*” is an attention framing, to shift the focus of the reader to the statistics of Vini during 2023-24. The second clause, “*He was the joint-eighth top-scorer in La Liga*”, states a contrast framing being only the eighth-top scorer rather than leading. The next clause, “*behind, among others a Norwegian fella who couldn’t get a game for Crystal Palace a few years ago,*” strengthens this frame through contrast and metaphor framing, by comparing Vini unfavorably to an unnamed, unfamiliar Norwegian player, representing Vini’s success as uninspiring. The clause, “*In the Champions League, the Brazilian scored six goals*”, presenting Vini as “*the Brazilian*” separates him personally and racializes the evaluation, which is a hidden discursive move sometimes utilized for other non-European players. The subsequent clause “*one more than Stoke reject Joselu, who played 628 minutes fewer*” sustains the comparison frame, stating “*Stoke reject Joselu*” and emphasizing a lesser number of minutes to diminish the six-goal record of Vini. The sixth clause, “*At the Copa America he scored twice in the group stages,*” uses artifact framing by showing factual information (two goals), but the alliance and brevity with clause seven, “*suspension and absence,*” create a failure frame. The final clause reveals the disciplinary issues of Vini, representing him as unreliable or irresponsible.

This extract at the explanation stage discursively depicts Vini as falling short of expectations, regardless of his accomplishments. Even though he wins and scores, the narrative diminishes these achievements by means of comparative criticism and portrays perceived failure. Based on CRT, such matter can be revealed in the social construction of race; Black players sometimes have to distance away from their peers to gain equivalent recognition, and even their accomplishments are depicted doubtfully. By presenting him as “*the Brazilian*” and highlighting issues of “*suspension*”, the media racialized and separated Vini. The concern about minor failure and the mockery “*stoke reject*” illustrates how marginalized figures are held to higher, sometimes

unachievable standards, associated with interest convergence. Eventually, the extract uncovers Vini not as a hero of strength but as a player whose worth is questioned, instead of tangible success.

4.2 Analysis of the American journals

4.2.1 The New York Times News Sports Reports, Report (1): “Vinicius Jr’s Ballon d’Or chances harmed by success of Real Madrid team-mates, awards chief suggests”

4.2.1.1 Extract (1):

France Football’s editor-in-chief Vincent Garcia has suggested that Vinicius Junior’s chances of winning the Ballon d’Or were harmed by the achievements of Real Madrid team-mates Jude Bellingham and Dani Carvajal. Vinicius Jr had been the favourite to win the men’s award, which is presented by France Football, before it emerged ahead of Monday’s ceremony in Paris that Manchester City midfielder Rodri was to receive the accolade.

Regarding the description stage the first clause, “*France Football’s editor-in-chief Vincent Garcia has suggested that Vinicius Junior’s chances of winning the Ballon d’Or were harmed by the achievements of Real Madrid team-mates Jude Bellingham and Dani Carvajal,*” is in declarative mood. It contains two processes, the verbal process is “*has suggested*”, with “*Vincent Garcia*” as the sayer, and the whole subordinate clause as the verbiage. Also, within the reported clause, there’s a relational process “*were harmed*”, the carrier is “*Vinicius Junior’s chances*”, where the attribute is “*harmed*” which expressed by a passive construction. The actor causing the harm is “*the achievements of Real Madrid team-mates Jude Bellingham and Dani Carvajal*” making it a material process embedded within the relational process. The system of appraisal utilizes engagement (reporting the view of Gracia), and a negative attitude (the loss of Vini is depicted as an outcome of others’ success). The theme is the clause “*France Football’s editor-in-chief Vincent Garcia has suggested that Vinicius Junior’s chances of winning the Ballon d’Or were harmed by the achievements of Real Madrid team-mates Jude Bellingham and Dani Carvajal*”. While rheme

asserts the cause of the presumed damage and the success of others. The passive constructions hide agency and faintly suggest that Vini lost because of the internal competition.

The next clause, “*Vinicius Jr had been the favourite to win the men’s award, which is presented by France Football*”, is declarative. It includes a relational process “*had been the favourite*”, the carrier is “*Vinicius Jr*”, and the attribute is represented in “*the favourite to win the men’s award*”. It also holds a non-defining relative clause “*which is presented by France Football*”, which involves a material process “*is presented*”, and the actor “*France Football*”, while the goal is the “*award*”. The appraisal system revolves around a positive attitude towards Vini (he was the favourite), and there is an engagement through which the clause states background info that authorizes the award’s status. The theme is the central clause “*Vinicius Jr had been the favourite to win the men’s award*”, while the rheme highlights his expected victory. The relative clause “*which is presented by France Football*” contains its own theme/rheme, presenting factual background about the validity of the award.

The final clause, “*before it emerged ahead of Monday’s ceremony in Paris that Manchester City midfielder Rodri was to receive the accolade*”, is in declarative mood. The central process is mental, “*it emerged*” with a non-human senser “*it*”. The embedded clause “*that Manchester City midfielder Rodri was to receive the accolade*” includes an existential process “*was to receive*”, the actor is “*Rodri*”, and the goal is “*the accolade*”. The modality is expressed by a modal verb phrase “*was to*”, which suggests an expectation or prediction. The appraisal system is neutral, while engagement is high. The theme is “*before it emerged ahead of Monday’s ceremony in Paris that Manchester City midfielder Rodri was to receive the accolade*”, and the rheme recognizes the disappointing or surprising twist; Vini will not win the award.

As far as the interpretation stage is concerned, in the first clause, “*France Football’s editor-in-chief Vincent Garcia has suggested that Vinicius Junior’s chances of winning the Ballon d’Or were harmed by the achievements of Real Madrid team-mates Jude Bellingham and Dani Carvajal*” contains a spin technique, which is used to soften the claim that Vini was harmed, affirming that it was not bias but team competition. This states a contrast frame, through which Vini’s loss of the award was not because of external racism, but because of teammates’ success. The second clause, “*Vinicius Jr had been the favourite to win the men’s award, which is presented by France Football,*” contains an artifact frame through “*favourite to win*”. Although by mentioning the role of France Football in stating the award. The final clause, “*before it emerged ahead of Monday’s ceremony in Paris that Manchester City midfielder Rodri was to receive the accolade,*” employs a storytelling and contrast frame. It establishes the expectation of Vini’s winning, who was later excluded by Rodri. Generally, the media frames the loss as internal and institutional, instead of racial issues, avoiding controversial implications.

The extract at the explanation stage demonstrates the way racial bias can be hidden in elite discourse via language that covers agency and neutralizes judgment. Yet, Vini was a top nominee, and his displacement is explained away by the success of others and ambiguous institutional mechanisms. This conforms to the CRT principle of interest convergence, in which racial might happens when it is associated with institutional interests. The constant use of passive construction and the absence of any reference to injustice or racism shows the ordinariness of racism. The extract redefines the loss as an effect of a system based on merit, and avoids mentioning the way racism may influence evaluations of merit. Therefore, the ideology that contributes to the exclusion of Vini is hidden through language, enhancing systems of privilege while revealing neutral and objective.

4.2.1.2 Extract (2):

After the news broke of Rodri's expected win on Monday afternoon, it also emerged that Madrid had decided to cancel their trip to Paris for the awards having previously been expected to take a delegation of 50. *The Athletic* reported that the decision was taken on Sunday after Madrid found out and meant that no-one from the Spanish side was there to accept the award for best club in the 2023-24 season, nor was Carlo Ancelotti present to receive his award for best men's coach.

During the description, the first clause, "*After the news broke of Rodri's expected win on Monday afternoon*", is in declarative mood and it is a dependent temporal clause. It contains a material process "*broke*", the actor is "*the news*", and "*of Rodri's expected win*" is a circumstantial extension illustrating the content of the event. The theme is the clause "*After the news broke of Rodri's expected win on Monday afternoon*", and the rheme presents a background for the institutional reaction.

The next clause, "*it also emerged that Madrid had decided to cancel their trip to Paris for the awards*", is declarative. It contains a mental process "*emerged*" in a pseudo-existential structure. The pronoun "*it*" is an empty subject; thus, the senser is not specified. The embedded clause "*Madrid had decided to cancel their trip to Paris*" includes a mental process "*had decided*", the senser is "*Madrid*", and another mental process "*to cancel*", with a goal "*their trip to Paris*". The verb phrase "*had decided*" reveals internal resolution and evaluation, uncovering intentionality. The appraisal system has a negative attitude. The theme is the full clause "*it also emerged that Madrid had decided to cancel their trip to Paris for the awards*", while the rheme expresses the institutional disappointment of Madrid.

The third clause, "*having previously been expected to take a delegation of 50*", is a dependent circumstantial clause in passive construction. It involves a relational process "*been expected*", the carrier "*Madrid*" is implicit, the attribute is "*to take a delegation of 50*". The modality is mentioned via the modal verb "*expected*", expressing obligation or probability. Such a

clause serves a circumstance of contrast. The theme is “*having previously been expected to take a delegation of 50*”, and the rheme states the expectation that was overturned.

The other clause, “*The Athletic reported that the decision was taken on Sunday after Madrid found out*”, is declarative. It contains a verbal process “*reported*”, the sayer is “*The Athletic*”, and the verbiage is “*the decision was taken on Sunday after Madrid found out*”. Within this embedded clause, there is a material process “*was taken*” in passive voice. Another process which mental “*Madrid found out*”, the sensor is “*Madrid*”, and the phenomenon is implied. The theme is “*The Athletic reported that the decision was taken on Sunday after Madrid found out*”, and the rheme emphasizes a delayed but received choice.

The final compound clause is “*and meant that no-one from the Spanish side was there to accept the award for best club in the 2023-24 season, nor was Carlo Ancelotti present to receive his award for best men’s coach*”. It involves a declarative mood, and relational process “*meant that*”, and other material processes “*to accept, to receive*”. Also, two actors, “*no-one from the Spanish side, Carlo Ancelotti*” are withdrawing or absent, which dramatizes the emotional and symbolic rejection. The theme is the full clause “*and meant that no-one from the Spanish side was there to accept the award for best club in the 2023-24 season, nor was Carlo Ancelotti present to receive his award for best men’s coach*”. The rheme expresses an important political absence in response to perceived injustice.

In the interpretation stage, the extract uses various framing techniques that form the reader’s recognition of Madrid’s absence not as petty or irrational, but as institutional and calculated. The first clause, “*After the news broke of Rodri’s expected win on Monday afternoon*”, creates a contextual framing. States a temporal background and asserts that the expected consequence (Rodri’s win) shaped subsequent decisions. Spin framing employed through “*emerged, was expected*”, which states the actions and judgments as inevitable or organic to reduce

the visibility or protest. The clause “*it also emerged that Madrid had decided to cancel their trip to Paris for the awards*”, specifically in “*Madrid had decided to cancel their trip*”, functions as a contrast framing. This makes a shift from expected celebratory participation, “*a delegation of 50,*” to withdrawal. The framing of this withdrawal as a decision taken “*after Madrid found out*” creates a cause-and-effect relation, inviting the reader to illustrate Madrid’s absence as a form of non-verbal opposition. Eventually, the lack of institutional presence, “*no-one from the Spanish side, Carlo Ancelotti,*” is framed as a symbolic absence. It creates an artifact frame around participation, assuming that not attending the ceremony event has meaning beyond logistics. The framing softens the confrontation while indirectly stating discontent, allowing the media to sustain (neutral) though reporting a politically loaded situation.

At the explanation stage, the extract emphasizes the way elite institutions like Real Madrid might be involved in implicit protest against perceived injustice; thus, the language of the report covers the racial dimension of the controversy. Instead of mentioning why Vini, a Black Brazilian who has been the target of determined racism, did not win the Ballon d’Or. The text represents Madrid’s absence from team dynamics and technical disappointment. Such a rhetorical strategy conforms to the principles of CRT of interest convergence; Madrid seems to protest only when its institutional pride is influenced. Moreover, the repetition of passive and non-agentive language “*was taken, emerged*”, uncovers the ordinaries of racism. Through implicitly naming it, the racial component becomes invisible and normalized. However, the institutional withdrawal could be illustrated as a symbolic solidarity with Vini, the framing struggles of this reading, choosing rather to state the event as a simple political case. Consequently, the text neutralizes the racial injustice and repositions the focus to the institution’s reaction, not the racialized individual at the core of the controversy.

4.2.1.3 Report (2): Extract (1): “Vinicius Junior, Ballon d’Or disappointment and Real Madrid’s furious reaction”.

“I think there are problems between Real Madrid and UEFA, which affected some things in the results,” former Madrid midfielder Clarence Seedorf told TNT Sports on the red carpet in Paris. “Vinicius Junior is the one who definitely deserves the award. It is a shame.”

As far as the description stage is concerned, the first clause, “*I think there are problems between Real Madrid and UEFA*”, is declarative. The mental process is “*think*”, the senser is “*I*”, and the phenomenon is “*there are problems between Real Madrid and UEFA*”. The clause involves an existential process “*there are*”, where “*problems between Real Madrid and UEFA*” serves as the existent. Low epistemic modality is stated via the mental process “*think*”, revealing personal opinion or uncertainty. The system of appraisal encompasses engagement (expressing the personal view of Seedorf) and attitude, as well as demonstrating concern or criticism of institutional relations. The theme is the full clause “*I think there are problems between Real Madrid and UEFA*”, where rheme uncovers the controversial notion of external institutional conflict.

The next clause, “*which affected some things in the results*”, is a dependent relative clause in declarative mood, modifying (problems). It contains a material process “*affected*”, where “*which*” refers to the problems as the actor, and the goal is “*some things in the results*”. The appraisal system involves a negative attitude, showing that hidden conflicts distort outcomes. The theme is “*which affected some things in the results*”, while the rheme emphasizes the effect of institutional politics on outcomes.

The third clause, “*Vinicius Junior is the one who definitely deserves the award*”, is declarative. It involves a relational identifying process “*is*”, where “*Vinicius Junior*” is the identifier, and “*the one who definitely deserves the award*” is the identified. Within the embedded clause, there is a mental process “*deserves*”, emphasizing a value judgement. The use of the modal

adverb “*definitely*” expresses high modality (certainty). The appraisal system includes a strong positive attitude regarding Vini, enhancing merit and legitimacy. The theme is “*Vinicius Junior is the one who definitely deserves the award*”, where the rheme emphasizes the claim of rightful recognition.

The final clause, “*it is a shame*”, is declarative. It involves a relational process “*is*”, where “*it*” is the carrier, and “*shame*” is the attribute. It entails a strong negative judgment; the attitude is evaluative and emotional. The theme is “*it is a shame*”, where the rheme provides the moral evaluations of injustice.

The extract at the interpretation stage, revolves around storytelling and contrast framing. Seedorf is the framing agent who constructs a counter-narrative to the official result. By saying “*I think there are problems between Real Madrid and UEFA*”, the clause highlights institutional conflict framing, assuming that politics within football rankings, not merit, determined the outcome. The second clause, “*which affected some things in the results*”, employs spin farming.

With a negative connotation that states bias or interference without directly accusing of corruption. This sustains a tone of professionalism while questioning fairness. Seedorf’s saying “*Vinicius Junior is the one who definitely deserves the award*”, involves slogan framing. A clear, strong, evaluative language that affirms merit and moral worth to Vini. The adverb “*definitely*” shows assertion, affirming the issue of racial discrimination and describing it as shameful. Eventually, the clause “*it is a shame*” evokes a contrast frame, contrasting what happened (Vini’s loss) with what really did for his team. The phrase becomes an influential result that encompasses emotional disappointment, constructing a moral frame against an unjust outcome. Along with the frames influencing the reader’s comprehension, the narrative is about institutional bias, where a deserving Black player is denied because of politics.

During the explanation stage, Seedorf's remarks reveal the way power dynamics, institutional interest, and racial positioning integrate in elite football. His statements align with the CRT principles of Interest convergence. Proposing that UEFA and Real Madrid's relationship may influence the result more than Vini's individual performance. Furthermore, Seedorf's strong support of Vini "*definitely deserves the award*," shows the unique voice of color. A voice of insider critique that emphasizes racial marginalization. The use of ambiguous references, "*problems, some things*", indicates the ordinary of racism in sports. Eventually, the phrase "*it is a shame*" states a legal storytelling, a personal narrative employed to challenge the dominant frame. According to Seedorf's voice, it is clear how a deserving Black player is marginalized through coded power structures, uncovering the ideological nature of recognition and merit in European football discourse.

4.2.1.4 Extract (2):

Winning the Champions League (involved in 11 goals in 10 games, including one in the final), La Liga (involved in 21 goals in 26 games, one every 89 minutes on average) and the Spanish Super Cup (hat-trick in the final against Barcelona) was not enough. So what would be?

As far as the description stage is concerned, the non-finite gerund clause, "*Wining the Champions League (involved in 11 goals in 10 games, including one in the final), La Liga (involved in 21 goals in 26 games, one every 89 minutes on average) and the Spanish Super Cup (hat-trick in the final against Barcelona) was not enough*", is a declarative. It serves as a single complex unit listing achievements and concluding with their evaluations. The central relational process is "*was not*", the carrier is the whole nominal group "*Wining the Champions League., La Liga., and the Spanish Super Cup..*", and the attribute is "*enough*". The appraisal system has a negative attitude; outstanding achievements are stated as insufficient. The theme is the full clause, while the rheme

“*was not enough*”, carrying the evaluative judgement. The implications are that even significant, measurable achievements do not guarantee recognition.

The other clause, “*So what would be?*”, is an interrogative clause, a rhetorical question. It contains a relational process “*would be*”, the carrier is absent, where the attribute is not stated. The use of the modal verb “*would*” expresses hypothetical modality, assuming doubt. The appraisal system operates here via engagement and attitude, challenging the criteria for merit. The theme is “*So what would be*”, a complete sentence that serves as a thematic and rhetorical shift, where the rheme critiques the judgment against Vini.

In the interpretation stage, the extract is formed with clear contrast framing. The structure contrasts massive success (quantifiable and widely recognized) with the final clause. This is an instance of contrast framing, where the recognition (the level of success ensures victory) is destroyed by the reported outcome. Which constructs a frame of injustice and disbeliefs. The rhetorical question “*So what would be*” reinforces the storytelling frame (the reader is asked to show the way absurd the denial is, stating that no accomplishments would have been enough in this context). Additionally, the statistics and performance details frame Vini not only as accomplished but extraordinary and exceptional. A spin framing is also crucial, through using a negative phrase, “*was not enough*,” which portrays the decision makers as biased or unreasonable.

At the explanation stage, the whole extract influentially demonstrates the CRT principle of interest convergence; although measurable success at the highest levels of European football, Vini is denied recognition. His excellence does not conform to dominant institutional interest, probably because it challenges rooted racial and regional levels. The relational clause, “*was not enough*,” linguistically represents this ideology (no matter how much is achieved, it is insufficient when excellence is evaluated by biased systems). The rhetorical question “*So what would be*” represents legal storytelling. It positions to shared logic and exposes the unreasonable nature of excellence

judgment when employed against racialized individuals. This clause also demonstrates the ordinary of racism; exclusion happens through strategic undervaluation, denial, and rejection. The extract creates a soft but powerful case for the way structural inequality is continued and covered in elite football awards discourse.

4.2.2 Analysis of ESPN

4.2.2.1 Report (1): Extract (1): “Ballon d’Or: Real Madrid, Brazil stars back Vinicius after snub”

A club source told ESPN the result was "unfair" and "shameful," calling it "a historic robbery." Vinicius posted on social media later on Monday, saying "I'll do it 10x if I have to. They aren't ready."

At the description level, the first clause, “*A club source told ESPN the result was ‘unfair’ and ‘shameful,’*” is declarative. It involves a verbal process “*told*”, with the sayer “*A club source*”, the receiver is “*ESPN*”, and the verbiage is the assessment of the result. In such a clause, “*the result was ‘unfair’ and ‘shameful,’*”, there is a relational process “*was*”, the carrier is “*the result*”, and the attributes are “*unfair’ and ‘shameful*”. Such attributes show strong attitude values, certainly in the appraisal system reflects negative judgment. The theme is the full clause, “*A club source told ESPN the result was ‘unfair’ and ‘shameful,’*”, where the rheme states an institutional voice condemning the result.

The next clause, “*calling a historic robbery*”, is an elliptical declarative clause. It contains a verbal process “*calling*”, alongside the recognized sayer being “*A club source*” from the previous clause, and “*it*”, which is the result as the verbiage. The phrase “*a historic robbery*” is a normalized evaluative phrase, which implies the negativity of the prior judgment. The system of appraisal reveals a strong attitude (judgment, outrage), and the use of “*historic*” suggests graduation. The

theme is “*calling a historic robbery*”, and the rheme enhances the institutional and ethical power of the reaction.

The third clause, “*Vinicius posted on social media later on Monday*”, is in declarative mood. It holds a material process “*posted*”, where “*Vinicius*” is the actor, and “*on social media*” is the circumstance. The crucial content of his post is in the next clause. The theme is the full clause “*Vinicius posted on social media later on Monday*”, where the rheme creates context for the direct quote.

The final clause, “*saying I’ll do it 10x if I have to. They aren’t ready.*”, is declarative. Includes a verbal process “*saying*”, alongside “*Vinicius*” as the sayer. There is a material process “*do*”, together with “*I*” as the actor, and “*it*” as the goal. The modality is reflected in “*I’ll*” (will), and “*if I have to*”, stating a medium willingness and obligation. In the phrase “*They aren’t ready,*” there is a relational process “*aren’t*”, alongside “*they*” as the carrier, and “*ready*” as the attribute. In the system of appraisal, there is an assertive and defiant attitude and engagement. The theme is “*saying I’ll do it 10x if I have to. They aren’t ready*”, while the rheme involves the ideological and emotional response of Vini to perceived injustice.

At the interpretation level, aligning with FT, the extract utilized various techniques to create an emotionally charged narrative of injustice. Initially, the verbal process “*told ESPN*” states a storytelling framing, assigning strong evaluative language “*unfair, shameful, historic robbery*” to the unnamed club source, forming institutional credibility. The phrase “*historic robbery*” employs metaphor framing, presenting a narrative of victimization and theft, implying the rhetorical influence of the discontent of the club. When the narrative changes to the direct voice of Vini, the framing becomes more personal. Vini’s statement, “*I’ll do it 10x if I have to,*” serves as a slogan or catchphrase, framed via numerical symbolism and repetition. It claims resilience and

persistence, presenting defiance. The clause, “*They aren’t ready,*” presents a contrast framing, asserting a gap between the system’s preparation and Vini’s force for his challenge.

At the explanation level with CRT, the extract uncovers the way individual voice and institutional voice create a discourse of resistance to perceived injustice. The language used by the club source reveals the unique voice of color, not in racial identity as such, but in its function of naming injustice and naming it as theft. The phrase “*historic robbery*” suggests that this is not a singular problem but part of a larger system, conforming to another principle of CRT, which is ordinary of racism. Vini’s response represents legal storytelling; he speaks not with official argument but with performative language, a short and direct message that reveals opposition and determination. His words, “*They aren’t ready,*” show the social construction of race; his resistance and identity are framed as very powerful for the dominant system to recognize comfortably. The rhetorical language of his post asserts that recognition and success are conditional, not on merit, but on institutional willingness to accept a Black player who resists racism. In this regard, the clause uncovers both ideological exclusion and discursive resistance, a fundamental theme in CRT.

4.2.2.2 Extract (2)

"Unfortunately, due to criteria that no one can understand, the award did not come. And don't get me wrong, Rodri is a great player, who deserves to be among the best. But Vini not winning this Ballon d'Or was embarrassing, and the only thing that lost today was football."

In regard to the description stage, the first clause, “*Unfortunately, due to criteria that no one can understand, the award did not come*”, is declarative and starts with the textual theme “*Unfortunately,*” which indicates a negative evaluation. The relational process is indicated by “*did not come*”, where “*the award*” serves as the carrier, and to Vini as the attribute. The subordinate

clause “*due to criteria that no one can understand*” involves a mental process “*understand*”, where “*no one*” is the senser, and “*criteria*” is the phenomenon. The modality expressed via negation “*no one can*,” implying the way probability and epistemic doubt. The appraisal system embeds strong negative judgment; the clause suggests the decision lacks logic or transparency. The theme is the whole clause “*Unfortunately, due to criteria that no one can understand, the award did not come*”, and the rheme reveals the critique of the process by which the award was decided.

The next clause, “*And don't get me wrong*”, is an imperative clause. It contains a mental process “*get*”, the phenomenon is “*me*”, and “*you*” as the senser. The clause serves interpersonally, implying engagement and softening the tone. There is modality via the negation “*don't*” signaling prevention instead of assertion. The theme is “*And don't get me wrong*”, while the rheme functions to explain the speaker's stance before further critique.

The third clause, “*Rodri is a great player, who deserves to be among the best*,” is in declarative mood. It includes two processes, relational and mental. “*Rodri is a great player*” involves a relational identifying process, where “*Rodri*” is the carrier, and “*a great player*” as the attribute. The relative clause “*who deserves to be among the best*” includes a mental process “*deserves*” with “*who*” (Rodri) as the senser, and the phenomenon being “*to be among the best*”. The modal verb “*deserves*” signals medium modality. The system of appraisal is a positive attitude, asserting Rodri's merit. The theme is the whole clause “*Rodri is a great player, who deserves to be among the best*”, where the rheme affirms that the criticism is not personal toward Rodri.

The other clause, “*But Vini not winning this Ballon d'Or was embarrassing*”, is declarative. It involves a relational process “*was*”, alongside the carrier being the normalized clause “*Vini not winning this Ballon d'Or was embarrassing*”, and the attribute being “*embarrassing*”. This expresses a strong negative attitude, showing emotional and ethical disapproval. The theme is “*But*

Vini not winning this Ballon d'Or was embarrassing", and the rheme suggests the judgment of the result's inappropriateness.

The final clause, "*and the only thing that lost today was football*", is also declarative. It includes a relational process "*was*", the carrier "*the only thing that lost today*", and the attribute is "*football*". This metaphoric construction reveals a relational attribution, affirming that the sport has suffered not only the player. The appraisal system here is symbolic and negative, with graduation reinforcing the intensity "*only thing*". The theme is the full clause "*and the only thing that lost today was football*", and the rheme highlights a wider cultural and social impact beyond individual loss.

The extract at the interpretation level utilizes contrast and metaphor framing as well as moral evaluation to construct an influential narrative. In the first clause, "*the award did not come*" minimizes agency via passive construction, where "*criteria that no one can understand*" refers to a spin framing obscuring decision-making in ambiguity. The contrastive phrase "*don't get me wrong*" frames the speaker as ethically justified, proactively blocking criticism. The statement "*Rodri is a great player*" functions as a balancing frame, recognizing Rodri's value to isolate the speaker from accusations of bias. The framing increases in the clause "*Vini not winning this Ballon d'Or was embarrassing*," where the contrast with Rodri is made direct, and the emotional framing succeeds. The lexical word "*embarrassing*" serves as a slogan, condensing ethical critique into a simple phrase. The final sentence, "*the only thing that lost today was football*," is an influential metaphor frame. It changes the problem from individual injustice to a symbolic loss for the sport itself, thus evaluating the risks of the argument and appealing to a broader audience. Generally speaking, the extract is framed not as a personal complaint but as an institutional failure that damages the legitimacy of football awards.

Concerning the explanation stage, the extract demonstrates how symbolic injustice functions within racialized structures of recognition. The phrase “*criteria that no one can understand*” conforms to CRT’s concept of institutional obscurity. Through which the rules seem neutral but serve to exclude racialized individuals. The accomplishments of Vini are minimized via unclear merit standards, revealing the interest convergence principle: recognition and awards are distributed when they correspond to dominant group interests, not when racialized individuals have received them. The clause “*Vini not winning this Ballon d’Or was embarrassing*” conveys emotional and ethical dimensions of exclusion. The absence of transparency, balancing with the declaration that football itself “*lost*”, uncovers how bias influences not only the individual but the institution’s honesty. The extract aims to assert Rodri’s talent while criticizing the result shows a racial bind, Vini should exceed dominant expectations, yet is denied even when he does. This analysis reveals that Vini is represented as both a performer and a symbolic challenge to Eurocentric beliefs in football. His pivotal rejection is framed not as individual failure but as a racialized denial of belonging, exposing the ideology included in the award system itself.

4.2.2.3 Report (2): Extract (1): “Can Vinicius Jr. rise above Ballon d’Or snub? It’s up to him”

There's a long and glorious history of the greats in life using failure, rejection and criticism to spur them on to heights that, perhaps, they wouldn't have achieved without facing what they considered to be gross unfairness. The question now is whether Vinicius Júnior is about to join the ranks of those who suffered "the slings and arrows of life's outrageous fortunes" and retorted, defiantly, with: "Is that really all you've got?"

As far as the description stage is concerned, the first declarative clause is, “*There’s a long and glorious history of the greats in life using failure, rejection and criticism to spur them on to heights that, perhaps, they wouldn’t have achieved without facing what they considered to be gross unfairness*”. It starts with an existential process “*there’s*”, the existent is “*a long and glorious*

history of the greats in life using failure... ”. It involves an embedded clause, “the greats in life using failure, rejection and criticism to spur them on to heights”. This clause includes material processes, “using, spur on”, the actors “the greats in life”, and “failure, rejection and criticism” are means that trigger another process, “spur them on to heights”. The clause, “they wouldn’t have achieved”, contains a material process “achieved”, alongside “they” as the actors, and “heights” as the goal. It is emphasized by a conditional modality “wouldn’t have” that triggers low certainty. An additional mental process is embedded in “they considered to be gross unfairness”, where “they” are sensors, and “gross unfairness” is the phenomenon. The whole clause involves comprehensive appraisal resources; attitude is positive through the resilience of the “greats” and negative toward the treatment they sustained “gross unfairness”. Engagement is revealed via the softening modal “perhaps” allowing alternative perspectives. The theme is the full clause, “There’s a long and glorious history of the greats..”, and the rheme develops a philosophical and motivational framework based on overcoming adversity. Overall, the tone is inspirational and evaluative.

The second clause, “*The question now is whether Vinicius Junior is about to join the ranks of those who suffered ‘the slings and arrows of life’s outrageous fortunes’ and retorted, defiantly, with: ‘is that really all you’ve got?’*”, is also declarative. It includes a relational identifying process “is”, where “The question” is the carrier and the identified is the nominal clause “*whether Vinicius Junior is about to join...*”. This embedded clause includes a material process “join”, alongside “Vinicius” as the actor, and the subordinate clause “*the ranks of those who suffered..*” as the goal. This clause involves a material process “suffered”, alongside “those” as the actors, and “*the slings and arrows of life’s outrageous fortunes*” as the phenomenon. The final embedded clause, “*and retorted, defiantly, with: ‘is that really all you’ve got?’*” is a verbal process, alongside “those” also as the sayers, and “*is that really all you’ve got*” as the verbiage. The structure of the language constructs graduation (expanding the greatness of adversity), and attribute (heroism, challenge,

injustice). The use of metaphor “*the slings and arrows of life’s outrageous fortunes*” (a reference to Shakespeare) suggests a dramatic and moral positioning. The theme is the full clause, and the rheme encourages the reader into an evolving narrative of confrontation and legacy.

In regard to the interpretation stage, the extract creates an influential narrative framing, merging myth-making, contrast, and heroic metaphor. The first clause, “*There’s a long and glorious history of the greats in life using failure...*” draws on the storytelling frame. It embeds the present moment in a long tradition of greatness born from adversity. By mentioning “*the greats in life*”, the writer frames Vini as a probable figure of historical significance. The adversity “*failure, rejection, criticism*” is framed not as loss, but as a fuel for achievement. The insertion of “*gross unfairness*” constructs a contrast framing between the injustice faced and the achievement accomplished. In the second clause, “*The question now is whether Vinicius Junior is about to join the ranks of those who suffered...*”, the narrative increases via intertextual framing. The Shakespearean line “*the slings and arrows of life’s outrageous fortunes*” is a cultural metaphor, emphasizing noble suffering. The retort “*is that really all you’ve got?*” serves as a slogan, resistant, memorable, and sharp. The rhetorical framing represents Vini as a modern mythic figure, prepared to transform pain into legacy. The framing here changes from lamentation to systematic defiance, setting the player not just as a victim of unfairness but also as an emerging symbol of strength and historical importance.

The extract in the explanation stage faintly mentions certain principles of CRT via symbolic language and narrative alignment. Initially, it uncovers the ordinaries of racism; the experience of Vini is stated with a larger pattern of “*rejection, criticism*” that proceeds transformation. The clause, “*Vinicius Junior is about to join the ranks,*” triggers the CRT principle of the unique voice of color, affirming his resistance and struggle are not isolated but symbolic of a deeper social

reality. Vini's imagined response, "*Is that really all you've got?*" reveals legal storytelling. An individual, expressive style of resistance that critiques domination without official accusation. Therefore, the discourse elevates Vini from athlete to a normal young Black player enduring institutional injustice, still, probably rewriting his narrative via resilience and identity. This enhances the ideological weight of his journey in the Ballon d'Or argument and beyond.

4.2.2.4 Extract (2):

Vinicius swiftly used social media to proclaim: "I'll do 10 times more if I have to. They're not ready." A post viewed over 128 million times! Now, if he's preparing to inflict a tempest of brilliance on Madrid's rivals to "show" those who have done him "an injustice," it's worth reflecting on how just such circumstances have had a catalytic impact on a few high-achievers in these situations.

At the description stage, the first clause, at the description level, "*Vinicius swiftly used social media to proclaim: 'I'll do 10 times more if I have to. They're not ready'*", is declarative. It involves a material process "*used*", where "*Vinicius*" is the actor, and "*social media*" is the goal. The embedded verbal process "*to proclaim*" presents Vini as the sayer, and the direct quote remains as verbiage. In the direct quote "*I'll do 10 times more if I have to. They're not ready*", there is a material process which is "*do*", alongside the actor "*I*", and the goal "*10 times more*". It is modified by obligation modality "*if I have to*", and futurity "*I'll*". The following embedded clause "*They're not ready*" utilizes a relational process "*are*", alongside "*they*" as the carrier, and "*not ready*" as the attribute, expressing negative judgment. The system of appraisal involves a high attitude, assertive, challenging, and defiant. The repetition of "*I'll do 10 times more if I have to*" highlights graduation. The theme "*Vinicius swiftly used social media to proclaim: 'I'll do 10 times more if I have to. They're not ready'*", and the rheme triggers both the content and the action of resistance.

The next clause, "*A post viewed over 128 million times!*", is in declarative mood, and it is an exclamative elliptical clause. It contains a material process "*viewed*", alongside "*A post*" as the

goal, and the actor is implicit (the audience). This structure shows emphasis by bravery and intensity, revealing the reach and public response of Vini's voice. The appraisal system here was revealed through graduation "*over 128 million times*," highlighting amplification of effect. The theme is "*A post viewed over 128 million times*", where the rheme emphasizes its exceptional reception, enhancing the social visibility of his defiant statement.

The final clause, "*Now, if he's preparing to inflict a tempest of brilliance on Madrid's rivals to 'show' those who have done him 'an injustice,' it's worth reflecting on how just such circumstances have had a catalytic impact on a few high-achievers in these situations*", is a conditional declarative clause. It contains a main relational process "*it's worth reflecting*", alongside the phenomenon the subordinate clause, "*he's preparing to inflict a tempest...*". It involves a material process "*inflict*", where "*he*" is the actor, and "*a tempest of brilliance*" is the goal. The verbal process "*to 'show'*" presents intention, where "*those who have done him 'an injustice'*" is the receiver. As it includes another material process "*have done*", alongside "*those*" as the actors, and "*an injustice*" as the goal. The appraisal system here involves attitude (positive towards Vini's brilliance; negative towards injustice), graduation (metaphor, '*tempest*'), and engagement (inviting the reader into a reflective stance). The theme is the full clause, where the rheme suggests that these contexts drive greatness.

The extract at the interpretation level frames Vini as both hero and resister, utilizing multiple framing techniques to elevate his moral stance and voice. The first clause, "*Vinicius swiftly used social media to proclaim...*" frames his declarations "*I'll do 10 times more if I have to. They're not ready*" as a slogan frame. It is precise, emotionally charged, and memorable, highlighting his resilience and challenge to power. The utilization of contrast framing, Vini's readiness versus "*their*" unpreparedness positions him as self-confident and morally higher. The

next clause, “*A post viewed over 128 million times!*” involves an artifact frame; the post becomes a digital marker of resistance. The massive visibility of his voice frames Vini as a public agent challenging an unfair system. The third clause, “*Now, if he’s preparing to inflict a tempest of brilliance...*”, uses storytelling and metaphor framing. The phrase “*a tempest of brilliance*” functions as a heroic metaphor, asserting a retaliatory and unstoppable face. This creates a narrative framing where the performance of Vini becomes rhetorical revenge, a system of expressive justice.

At the explanation level, the extract uncovers the way racial injustice and resistance are discursively sustained in sports media. The statement of Vini, “*They’re not ready,*” faintly emphasizes the system, a hidden reference to football institutions or voters. This conforms to the CRT principle of social construction of race. Vini’s defiance is not neutral but is interpreted as transgressive within Eurocentric football culture. His statement, comprehensive, alongside assertive modality, as well as expresses the unique voice of color, personal evidence that challenges structural erasure. The reach of the post to “*128 million times*” explains the power of counternarrative and legal storytelling. The use of public digital platforms to state resistance and reclaim visibility. The metaphor “*a tempest of brilliance*” performs the performance of resilience, a form of resistance that recovers space via excellence. Finally, the clause “*those who have done him an injustice*” structures his experience in the language of systemic oppression, aligning with the CRT principle of interest convergence.

4.3 Discussion of Findings

This section presents a unified discussion of the findings arising from the CDA of the selected British and American sports journalism. The analysis focused on the depiction of Vini Jr. from the 2024 Ballon d’Or award. This study adopts an interdisciplinary framework consisting of Fairclough’s three-dimensional approach, Halliday’s SFL, Fairhurst and Sarr’s FT, and Delgado

and Stefancic's CRT. The current study uncovered the way language, framing, and ideology together create the narratives of race, merit, and power. Numerical details are presented through analytical tables at each stage to support the discussion.

4.3.1 Linguistic and Discursive Devices in British and American Sports Media

The analysis of the sixteen extracts showed important patterns in linguistic choices. As far as the mood system is concerned, specifically declarative clauses occurred in British journals 33 times, and in American journals 25 times, providing an assertive and authoritative style of reporting. Imperative clauses were used only three times in British and once in American, to express resistance or appeal. Interrogative clauses were rare and occurred only once in American, and were mostly rhetorical in tone. Regarding transitivity processes, material processes were the most utilized, 32 times in British, and 18 in American, emphasizing the actions performed or taken generally toward or via Vini. Relational processes occurred 19 times in British, and 16 in American journals and functioned as a conformation of qualities or values, such as assigning success or failure. Mental processes were identified 11 times in British and nine in American journals, which focused on thoughts, opinions, or judgments. Verbal processes occurred 11 times in British and eight in American, especially in the form of reported speech or evaluative commentary. Only one in the British and five in the American clauses utilized existential processes to present the state of being. In terms of modality, the modals such as "*may, possibility, and perhaps*" occurred seven times in British and 14 times in American, showing different degrees of certainty and obligation. Appraisal systems are also crucial; attitudinal judgements are used 12 times in British and 17 times in American journals. Engagements six times in British and nine in American journals, and graduations five times in British and six in American journals, in the reports selected. These findings assert that the discourse is constructed by linguistic patterns that obscure agency,

emphasizing evaluative stance, and negotiate agreement with resistance to dominant ideologies.

The following table summarizes the linguistic features from the description stage:

Table 8

Description Stage (Linguistic Devices)

Feature No.	Linguistic Devices	Frequency in British Reports	Frequency in American Reports
1	Declarative mood	33	25
2	Imperative mood	3	1
3	Interrogative mood		1
4	Material processes	32	18
5	Relational processes	19	16
6	Mental processes	11	8
7	Verbal processes	11	8
8	Existential processes	1	5
9	Modal verbs	7	14
10	Appraisal: attitude	12	17
11	Appraisal: Engagement	6	9
12	Appraisal: Graduation	5	6

4.3.2 Framing of Racism and Vinicius Junior in Media Narratives

Through the analysis of the 16 extracts, various framing techniques were used to affect the way readers understand Vini's identity, performance, and the controversy surrounding the Ballon d'Or award. The most used technique was contrast framing, which occurred 15 times in British journals and 11 in American journals to juxtapose expected merit with denied recognition or to mark Vini against others. Metaphor framing occurred six times in British, and nine in American journals, either to elevate Vini to the level of a mythic figure or to dramatize the injustice he endured. The spin framing was utilized four times in British and five in American, revising facts to state negative or positive connotations. Slogans and catchphrases occurred four times only in British journals, represented through Vini's direct speech, in order to sustain resistance and determination in memorable language. Artifacts occurred 3 times in British and nine in American, including reference to Vin's social media posts, offering symbolic weight to his counter-narratives. Storytelling frames were identified six times in British and five times in American. All of these techniques worked together to create a complex image of Vini, including both resistance and excellence, with exclusion and controversy. The media framing puts Vini as an athlete who defies institutional expectations, is occasionally admired, and is problematized. The next table summarizes the framing devices and their occurrence in the analyzed reports:

Table 9*Interpretation Stage (Framing Devices)*

Device No.	Framing Device	Frequency in British Reports	Frequency in American Reports
1	Contrast	15	11
2	Metaphor	6	9
3	Spin	4	5
4	Slogans and catchphrases	4	
5	Artifacts	3	9
6	Storytelling	6	5

4.3.3 Ideological Implications and Racial Dynamics in Media Representation

At the third level of analysis, the ideological implications declared by means of CRT stated a deeper comprehension of the way racial injustice was emphasized or concealed within the media texts. The principle of ordinary racism occurred only once in British journals, and five times in American journals, and it was evident in the way media discourse normalized Vini's mistreatment and injustice without naming it as racially motivated. Interest convergence occurred five times in British journals, and seven times in American journals, and was illustrated in the way recognition or support for Vini was only expanded when it conformed to larger institutional goals or public sentiment. The social construction of race occurred four times in British journals and two in American journals, showing the way Vini's identity as a young, Black, outspoken athlete formed how his merit and behavior were highlighted. The unique voice of color occurred twice in British journals and four times in American journals, specifically in direct quotes from Vini or those representing marginalized viewpoints. The legal storytelling and use of personalized narratives

occurred five times only in American journals, regularly as metaphorical or emotional resistance voiced by Vini through social media or public speech. Collectively, these findings reveal the ideological perspectives of the journals. The table below provides key points of ideological tools:

Table 10

Explanation Stage (Ideological Tools)

Principle No.	CRT Principles	Frequency in British Reports	Frequency in American Reports
1	Ordinaries of racism	1	5
2	Interest convergence	5	7
3	The social construction of race	4	2
4	The unique voice of color	2	4
5	Legal storytelling		5

As a result, the analysis reveals that British and American media reports use advanced linguistic, ideological, and rhetorical strategies to frame racialized players like Vini Jr. The text also challenges his visibility, emotional expression, and calls for justice. The findings through these three stages affirm that the denial of the Ballon d'Or was not a sports issue but a site of discursive struggle. Where race and ideology integrate to resist, produce, and enhance marginalization.

Chapter Five

Conclusions, Recommendations, and Suggestions for Further Research

5.0 Introduction

This chapter presents the conclusions arrived at after analyzing the selected British and American news reports to answer the research questions raised by the researcher and achieve the intended aims. In addition, some recommendations and suggestions for further research are stated clearly in the chapter.

5.1 Conclusions

This study attempts to identify the discursive and ideological construction of racism in British and American sports news reports tackling Vini's exclusion from the Ballon d'Or 2024. Based on the adopted model, including Fairclough's three-dimensional framework (1989, 2001), Halliday and Matthiessen's (2014), Fairhurst and Sarr's FT (1996), and Delgado and Stefancic's CRT (2001), the following conclusions have been arrived at to answer the proposed questions:

- 1- As far as research question (1) is concerned, the analysis indicated that both British and American journals depended heavily on the declarative mood, and various processes (material, relational, mental, existential, and Verbal). Specifically speaking, British media reports, on the one hand, frequently utilize material process, which indicates a strong focus on events, actions, and external voices. Many of these processes are formed in the passive voice, which withholds agency and responsibility for racism. This discursive strategy downplays the role of bias and racism through highlighting results instead of individual causes. On the other

hand, American journals used more direct racial dynamics. The material processes maintain clear actors and affected participants, making the agency (Ballon d'Or) accused of racism more visible. This visible case allows for a clearer representation of actions and consequences.

Relational process in the British journals was utilized to assign qualities, states, or identities to Vini and other players. These processes controlled the exclusion by comparing the performance of Vini to others. Whereas the American journals used the relational process similarly to define states or attributes, as they emphasize Vini's successes in statistical terms, carrying merits more strongly into focus.

In the British journals, mental processes were embedded or reported in thoughts, isolating the journalistic voice from sensitive decisions. Moreover, verbal processes were utilized to represent others' opinions, allowing racial issues to be raised implicitly in the journals. Alternatively, in American journals, the mental and verbal processes were crucial, specifically when mentioning quotes from the player (i.e., Vini), external commentators, or officials. These processes offered more voice to Vini's right to win the award. In the British journals, using the existential processes suggested a resistance to directly stating the existence of racism and injustice. Similarly, in American journals, the existential processes were used to refer to racism and injustice.

The modals in British and American journals stood for uncertainty and hedges, assigning caution or avoidance. Both journals relied on the declarative mood, suggesting a preference for authoritative statements that consider decisions as facts.

The appraisal system is portrayed in the British journals through the attitudinal judgements, engagements, and graduations, which are implicitly employed to downplay the significance of the events. The American journals revealed higher attitudinal engagements,

engagements, and graduations, which show a stronger emotional tone, as well as showing concern, sympathy, or admiration for Vini's activism.

In sum, the transitivity system in British journals sanitizes the discourse, protects institutional credibility, and marginalizes Vini's racial experience by portraying it on technical merit and separating it from direct critique. By contrast, the American journals employ transitivity to recognize the larger visibility of racial discourse, and framing Vini as a victim of injustice and a voice of resistance, rather than just a player.

2- To answer research question (2), the transitivity system for both British and American journals, specifically by material and relational processes, played an important role in forming how Vini was positioned. In media discourse, the lexical choices such as "*not enough, was denied, or embarrassing*" framed his exclusion from the Ballon d'Or as either surrounded by controversy or justified by performance. Verbs such as "*described, claimed, and reacted*" highlight emphasis upon external illustrations of his actions, often diminishing his activity. Using the evaluative and comparative phrases revealed underlying biases and depicted Vini's image as poor instead of completely merit-based.

3- Concerning research question (3), the framing of racism in both British and American sports journalism is conflicting, complicated, and shaped by various discursive beliefs and norms. In British media reports, contrast framing juxtaposes Vini's contributions with those of other players. These contrasts are set to imply that Vini's season was less deserving or incomplete. On the other hand, in the American journals, the contrast frames were used to question the fairness of the decision.

Metaphor framing in British journals was employed to soften or dramatize the narrative without naming racism explicitly. The metaphorical phrase, such as "*slings and arrows*," was utilized to create a distance between discourse and the factual accusations of

racial injustice; whereas in American journals, using metaphor framing was intended to state emotional tension. The metaphorical phrase, like “*tempest of brilliance*,” works to dramatize the injustice in a way that aligns with the emotions of unfair treatment. Spin framing in British journals states the emotional tone of specific events. The use of lexical items such as “*dramatic*, or *disrespectful*” in a way that undermines the validity of their protest against Vini’s exclusion. At the same time, in American journals, Vini’s resistance was framed positively, depicting him as a symbol of resilience instead of arrogance. Slogans and catchphrases occurred only in British journals originally from Vini himself, “*I will do it 10 times if I have to. They are not ready.*” This selective use de-emphasized the rhetorical force and represented them as reactive or excessive instead of empowering. Storytelling frame in British journals, focusing on Vini’s football journey or award statistics. In American journals, there were more emotionally charged elements involving personal resistance, struggle, and public perception. In addition, external voices were another device used instead of institutional voices.

Lastly, artifacts in British and American journals were used to uncover traditional reporting that avoids interrelated digital or visual representation in discourse. In sum, British journals, on the one hand, frame the Ballon d’Or decision via contrast and detachment, minimizing racial injustice and highlighting merit-based judgment. On the other hand, American journals emphasized racial implications and the portrayal of Vini as a victim through using metaphors and digital artifacts.

- 4- To answer research question (4), the ideological implications of racial dynamics concerned with the Ballon d’Or 2024 were portrayed through the lens of CRT. In British journals, the principle of ordinary racism indicated an institutional injustice to confront and recognize racism as a structural element in sport. By contrast, in American journals, using ordinary

racism reflects a stronger confession that racism was embedded in sport, specifically in La Liga and other institutions like the Ballon d'Or or UEFA. The interest convergence principle, used in British journals to support Vini. The American journals reacted differently, describing him as critiqued and problematized. Assert that institutions support racial fairness narratives only when they are associated with public image.

Moreover, the social construction of race principles in British and American journals reveals how Vini's identity was constructed explicitly and implicitly as a Black, young, and anti-racist player about his activism, marking him as "*others*" as compared to a more institutionally aligned figure. These portrayals stated racial boundaries. Furthermore, in British and American journals, using a unique color voice was portrayed through direct quotations from Vini or by reporting on his social media responses. Eventually, the legal storytelling principle used only in American journals presented Vini's words as counter-narratives to institutional silence or injustice, highlighting the role of Vini as a racial injustice advocate.

5.2 Recommendations

Various practical and academic recommendations can be proposed:

- 1- Sports communication instructors should encourage students to explore how discourse in sports writing forms public opinion on race, justice, and merit.
- 2- Sports journalists and editorial teams should develop comprehensive reporting strategies that account for racial bias. With implicit and explicit linguistic structures.
- 3- Media literacy programs should involve training on how to state and critique ideological framing in sports journalism, specifically concerning racial narratives.

5.3 Suggestions for Further Research

- 1- A Critical Discourse Analysis to investigate award discourse in global institutions, such as FIFA or UEFA.
- 2- Pragmatic study to explore the way speech acts are used in football journalism to reject or mitigate racism.
- 3- Pragma-stylistic analysis can be employed to study how stylistic features such as irony, metaphor, and intertextuality are strategically included in journalistic texts to form ideological perceptions.
- 4- A sociolinguistic study may investigate the way race, identity, and language variations impact the portrayal of athletes in global media.

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الْخَاصَّةُ

تُؤَدِّي الصَّحَافَةُ الرِّيَاضِيَّةُ فِي سِيَاقِ الْمَشْهَدِ الْإِعْلَامِيِّ وَطَيْفَةً تَفُوقُ مَجْرَدَ نَقْلِ النُّتَاجِ، فَهِيَ تَعْمَلُ كَمَنْصَّةٍ خَطَابِيَّةٍ مُؤَيَّدَةٍ تُسَاهِمُ فِي إِثْسَاءِ الْمَعْنَى الْاجْتِمَاعِيِّ، وَتُعَزِّزُ الْإِيدِيُولُوجِيَّاتِ السَّائِدَةِ، وَتُؤَيِّزُ فِي وَعِي الْجُمْهُورِ وَإِدْرَاكِهِ. وَتَهْدَفُ هَذِهِ الدِّرَاسَةُ إِلَى اسْتِفْصَاءِ كَيْفِيَّةِ تَأْطِيرِ الْعُنْصُرِيَّةِ وَالِدِيْنَامِيَّاتِ الْعِرْقِيَّةِ فِي التَّقَارِيرِ الْإِخْبَارِيَّةِ الرِّيَاضِيَّةِ، وَذَلِكَ بِشَكْلِ خَاصِّ فِي قَضِيَّةِ لَاعِبِ نَادِي رِيَالِ مَدْرِيدِ فِينِيْسِيُوسِ جُونِيُورِ (فِينِي جُونِيُورِ) وَاسْتِبْعَادِهِ مِنْ جَائِزَةِ الْكُرَّةِ الدَّهْبِيَّةِ لِعَامِ ٢٠٢٤ م. وَتَتَجَسَّدُ الْمَشْكَلَةُ الَّتِي تَتَنَاوَلُهَا هَذِهِ الدِّرَاسَةُ فِي الطَّرِيقَةِ الَّتِي يُعْرَسُ بِهَا الظُّلْمُ الْمُؤَسَّسِيُّ وَالتَّحْيِزُ الْعِرْقِيُّ فِي التَّقَارِيرِ الرِّيَاضِيَّةِ، وَفِي مَا إِذَا كَانَتْ هَذِهِ التَّقَارِيرُ تُنَاقِضُ هَذِهِ التَّحْيِزَاتِ أَمْ تُعَزِّزُهَا. وَبِنَاءِ عَلَى ذَلِكَ، تَسْعَى الدِّرَاسَةُ إِلَى تَحْدِيدِ الْاسْتِرَاتِيْجِيَّاتِ الْعُوقِيَّةِ وَالْخَطَابِيَّةِ الْمُسْتَخْدَمَةِ فِي التَّقَارِيرِ الرِّيَاضِيَّةِ الْبَرِيْطَانِيَّةِ وَالْأَمْرِيْكَئِيَّةِ الْمُخْتَارَةَ لِتَمَثِيلِ اسْتِبْعَادِ فِينِي مِنْ جَائِزَةِ الْكُرَّةِ الدَّهْبِيَّةِ لِعَامِ ٢٠٢٤ م. كَمَا تَسْتَفْصِي أَيْضًا أَدْوَارَ الْخِيَارَاتِ الْمُعْجَمِيَّةِ الْمُسْتَخْدَمَةِ فِي هَذِهِ التَّقَارِيرِ، وَكَيْفِيَّةِ تَأْطِيرِهَا لِلْعُنْصُرِيَّةِ. وَفِي نَهَآئَةِ الْأَمْرِ، تَسْتَكْشِفُ هَذِهِ الدِّرَاسَةُ النَّدَايَاتِ الْإِيدِيُولُوجِيَّةِ لِلدِّيْنَامِيَّاتِ الْعِرْقِيَّةِ الْمُرْتَبِطَةِ بِالْجَائِزَةِ، وَذَلِكَ مِنْ خِلَالِ مَنَهْجِ التَّحْلِيلِ النَّقْدِيِّ لِلْخَطَابِ (CDA). وَيَسْتَنْدُ تَحْلِيلُ الْبَيِّنَاتِ الْمُخْتَارَةَ إِلَى أَرْبَعَةِ أَسْئَلَةٍ، وَهِيَ: ١. مَا الْاسْتِرَاتِيْجِيَّاتُ الْخَطَابِيَّةُ وَالْعُوقِيَّةُ الْمُسْتَخْدَمَةُ مِنْ خِلَالِ نِظَامِ التَّعْدِيَّةِ لِتَصْوِيرِ اسْتِبْعَادِ فِينِي مِنْ جَائِزَةِ الْكُرَّةِ الدَّهْبِيَّةِ لِعَامِ ٢٠٢٤ م؟ ٢. مَا أَدْوَارُ الْجَوَانِبِ الْمُعْجَمِيَّةِ فِي تَمَثِيلِ الظُّلْمِ الْجَدْرِيِّ؟ ٣. كَيْفَ تُؤَطَّرُ الصُّحُفُ الْبَرِيْطَانِيَّةُ وَالْأَمْرِيْكَئِيَّةُ قَضِيَّةَ الْعُنْصُرِيَّةِ؟ ٤. مَا النَّدَايَاتُ الْإِيدِيُولُوجِيَّةُ الْمُرْتَبِطَةُ بِجَائِزَةِ الْكُرَّةِ الدَّهْبِيَّةِ لِعَامِ ٢٠٢٤ م؟

وَلِتَحْقِيقِ الْأَهْدَافِ وَالْإِجَابَةِ عَنِ الْأَسْئَلَةِ الْمَقْتَرَحَةِ، تَمَّ تَحْلِيلُ سِتَّةِ عَشَرَ (١٦) مُقْتَضًا مِنْ تَقْرِيرَيْنِ رِيَاضِيَّيْنِ بَرِيْطَانِيَّيْنِ، وَهُمَا "بي بي سي (BBC)" و"الغارديان (The Guardian)"، وَتَقْرِيرَيْنِ أَمْرِيْكَئِيَّيْنِ، وَهُمَا "إي إس بي إن (ESPN)" و"نيويورك تايمز (The New York Times)" وَقد أُجْرِيَتْ الدِّرَاسَةُ مِنْ خِلَالِ مَنَهْجِ بَحْثِيٍّ نَوْعِيٍّ يَسْتَخْدِمُ نَمُودَجًا انْتِقَائِيًّا، يَشْمَلُ: إِطَارَ فِيرْكُلُوفِ ذِي الْأَبْعَادِ الثَّلَاثَةِ (١٩٨٩، ٢٠٠١)، وَاللِّسَانِيَّاتِ الْوُظَيْفِيَّةِ الْنِظَامِيَّةِ لِهَالِيدَايِ وَمَايْسِنِ (٢٠١٤)، وَنَظْرِيَّةِ التَّأْطِيرِ لِفِيرْ هُورْست وَسَارِ (١٩٩٦)، وَنَظْرِيَّةِ الْعِرْقِ النَّقْدِيَّةِ لِديْلِعَانُو وَسْتِيْفَانْسِيْشِ (٢٠٠١). وَقد خَلَصَتْ نَتَائِجُ التَّحْلِيلِ إِلَى أَنَّ الصُّحُفَ الْبَرِيْطَانِيَّةَ وَالْأَمْرِيْكَئِيَّةَ تَبْنِي تَقَارِيرَهَا عَلَى الْعَمَلِيَّاتِ الْمَادِيَّةِ وَالْعِلَاقِيَّةِ، لِأَنَّهَا تَعْكِسُ الْعُنَاصِرَ الرَّئِيسِيَّةَ فِي تَمَثِيلِ الْأَفْعَالِ وَالْعِلَاقَاتِ فِي اللُّغَةِ. كَمَا أَنَّهُ، عَلَى الصَّعِيدِ الْإِيدِيُولُوجِيِّ، تَعْتَمِدُ التَّقَارِيرُ الْبَرِيْطَانِيَّةُ عَلَى التَّصْرِيحِ الصَّرِيحِ بِوُجُودِ الظُّلْمِ الْعِرْقِيِّ، فِيمَا تَرَكِزُ الصُّحُفَ الْأَمْرِيْكَئِيَّةُ عَلَى غُمُوضِ الْأَسْبَابِ الَّتِي تَقْفُ خَلْفَ الْعُنْصُرِيَّةِ، وَتَتَجَنَّبُ الْإِفْصَاحَ الْمُبَاشِرَ عَنِ التَّحْيِزِ الْعِرْقِيِّ. وَفِي الْخَتَامِ، تُقَدِّمُ الدِّرَاسَةُ مَجْمُوعَةً مِنَ التَّوَصِيَّاتِ وَالْمُقْتَرَحَاتِ لِلدِّرَاسَاتِ الْمُسْتَقْبَلِيَّةِ.

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كلية الآداب
قسم اللغة الإنجليزية وآدابها

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في اللغة الإنجليزية وعلم اللغة

الطالب

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